

Report on Research Line 2

Exploring behavioural change at places affected by biodiversity change from the perspective of vulnerable groups

Insights from ACCTING's Experimental Research

Research Cycle 2

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The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

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Disclaimer

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Introduction and methodology

This report presents a summary of findings from Research Line 7 of ACCTING's second cycle of experimental studies, which draws on data gathered from 87 quasi-experimental case studies conducted across thirteen countries between December 2023 and August 2024. Each research line explores sustainability and behavioural change within the framework of a specific European Green Deal policy area—including climate change, biodiversity, energy, food, and transport. This report focuses on biodiversity land use restriction and pro-nature change, and *more specifically on places and cases affected by biodiversity change where vulnerable people come together to engage in care-taking activities for nature*, examining how individual and collective behavioural change occurs while such care-taking actions are conducted by vulnerable people and/or in marginalised settings.

All reports are available at <https://accting.eu/project-deliverables/>

1. Introduction

Human-nature interaction is central to humanity and civilization. However, alarming voices on global warming and IPCC reports highlight the significant human impact on a global scale, marking a change unprecedented in recent decades. At the same time, scientists have long been sounding the alarm on the increasing loss of biodiversity, viewing it as a crisis as critical as climate change for the planet.

These considerations in mind, the focus of Research Line 2 (RL2) is on *“Exploring behavioural change appearing with the establishment of protected areas, with the aim to understand the match of biodiversity land use restrictions and socio-economic needs of vulnerable groups viewed from a gender+ perspective”*. RL2 concentrates on care for biodiversity and care for nature. Biodiversity change is physically closer to citizens, more visible in daily life than the more abstract climate change. When biodiversity is linked to humanity, cultural differences and different value systems make biodiversity an increasingly important topic in education, academical discourses, and reshape the responsibilities of specialised bodies such as IPBES, UNEP, also in language and discourses about what we actually mean with biodiversity.

A range of human centric concepts, and newer concepts like that of multispecies perspectives, have appeared in the past decades. Mostly not from the side of the natural sciences, but the social sciences and humanities (Van Dooren et al., 2016). Even the concept of "nature" itself is not universally understood (Ducarme et al., 2021), nor is the concept of wilderness in a conservation context. This presents a challenge for our work in RL2, as we are dealing with a subject whose meaning is fluid, and with interpretations that vary across different cultural contexts.

Figure 1 below shows the increasing complexity of terms with which researchers must deal when handling the concept of 'biodiversity'.

- Surrounding
- Outside
- Living place
- Nature
- Environment
- Ecology
- Plants, animals and land
- Wilderness
- Personal usage
- Personal value of nature
- Keeping nature intact
- Acting to protect
- Balancing interests of use and protecting
- Keeping nature for the future generations

Figure 1. Complexity of interaction of people with nature (own figure).

Considering this and building on the experiences from the first research cycle, where the research questions centred around human interaction with nature, nature protection and conservation, overall environmental challenges, and the role of agriculture, research cycle two **focuses on places and cases where active people come together and collectively engage in caretaking for nature.**

The central question is as follows: **“How do communities, groups, families, and individuals in vulnerable settings take care for nature?”** This inquiry touches on more “complex” issues, as illustrated in Figure 1 above, and looks for *explanations how change appears*. It does so by going in more depth than the first cycle research. We aim to understand explanations of **how behavioural change occurs within individuals but also collectively**, while taking a gendered perspective.

The following text box showcases the main research questions addressed by RL2 in the second research cycle:

How does *pro-nature behavioural change* emerge or change from the involvement in practical stewardship for nature activities, especially for the more vulnerable members of the society?

What are the *motivations* of individuals, vulnerable groups, to become active in environmental initiatives and what *triggers* involvement in activities of caretaking for nature?

How does *participation* in initiatives work and why is the engagement as a group and through specific roles important? How do joint activities relate to collective pro-nature behavioural change, especially among vulnerable groups?

What kind of *knowledge* enables people to become active in pro-nature and environmental stewardship?

How can the *knowledge dynamics* be explained? How is knowledge accessible, shared and related to specific roles, and how is knowledge utilised in practice by specific communities?

Can we observe fundamental *transformative change* that relate to active individuals or groups and what are important dynamics of change?

What are, if any, relevant *gender specific factors* for participation?

The novelty of our research process is that we include issues within the primary data collection process (interviews) that do not only impact “nature and biodiversity” but extend to broader contexts with significant real-life implications, particularly in cases where livelihoods and the environment are

challenged simultaneously. In such instances, people mobilise themselves to protect their livelihoods, ensure their socio-economic survival, and address governance, democracy, and last but not least, justice with multiple viewpoints. Our analysis puts a strong emphasis on better understanding the perceived complexity behind behavioural change in such situations. The initiatives studied in RL2 are focusing some part of their actions on behaviour change; i.e., an *observed change* that does not leave anybody behind.

We relate the "observed change" to the special role of vulnerable populations, citizens who, despite numerous challenges, begin to become active or organise themselves. Groups engage in actions not only for environmental protection or for pro-nature rationales but to safeguard their own livelihoods, reshaping their interaction with nature and developing a mindset for collectively managing specific natural sites/areas.

These "observed changes" occur in selected cases that work towards a variety of goals and contribute to different activities. Intentionally we use the terms *caretaking for nature* and *stewardship for nature* interchangeably in our report. Those terms have *nuanced differences* in meaning, especially in how they *frame human engagement with the environment*. We emphasise the *place-based approach* as a binding element and extend, where necessary, to broader regional or national developments that concern activist groups. Local developments often connect to national frameworks, including laws, specific governance structures, and the extent to which systems *support, permit or refuse* caretaking for nature activities.

2. Methodology: Case selection and interview process

RL2 followed a structured, stepwise methodological approach where each step was jointly agreed by the research team. The research team was composed of the same participating partners as in the first research cycle, covering identical countries conducting the 2nd research cycle of ACCTING. The 5 countries involved in the research were Bulgaria (ZSI), Hungary (ZSI), Portugal (IGOT), Romania (UIAC), and Türkiye (SU).

Our team of researchers had different backgrounds and thus approached the topic of "taking care of nature" from various academic fields such as sociology, gender studies, geography, psychology, landscape ecology. This range of experience and expertise brought several challenges; for instance, in the understanding of various terms, which necessitated a common template before and during the interview process.

To identify fitting case studies in the five countries, initial information was gathered by directly contacting initiatives, or indirectly accessing information from other studies or related projects or programmes. A standardised **template** was used to pre-describe and document the initial information on each case, leading to a full list of 11 cases that showcase unique methods of pro-nature activities.

The primary goal of all the cases is to **achieve a pro-nature change**. We aim to understand *how these initiatives engage vulnerable individuals or groups*. Before the interview phase, all national research teams documented the main pro-nature ambitions and activities of each case and strived to capture the local determining factors. This allowed for later integration of case-specific conditions in the cross-case analysis, presented below.

To capture the most important determinants of each case, the information was structured along seven key elements of information (see Table 1): (1) Results and main aims of interventions; (2) Resources; (3) Actors; (4) Power relations; (5) Time/speed and pace of action; (6) Participation aspects; (7) Additional insights on pro-nature stewardship activities were collected in a first step. A summary is given further below in Table 3.

Table 1. Main components for structuring the intervention logic of RL2 initiatives in RC2.

Initially captured information:	Description of the initially captured information	Reference in Table 1 as presented in the report and as <u>reference</u> for the RL2 report
(1) Result and aim	Describes the main goals related to pro-nature caretaking, the importance of a collective perspective; the role of vulnerabilities in the initiatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges and objectives • Main outcomes
(2) Resources	Identifies key enablers and hindrances for individuals or/and groups, focusing on framing resources that impact engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outcome factors • Characteristics
(3) Actors	Informs on supporters (and opponents), noting vulnerabilities of participants or groups, the potential influences from external bodies like authorities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outcome factors • Characteristics
(4) Power relations	Outlines leadership, power dynamics, (group) experience, legal powers, (non-)negotiable issues for involved groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main outcomes • Outcome factors • Characteristics
(5) Time/pace/speed	Describes triggers, urgency, whether it's a one-off or an ongoing effort, and initiatives preparedness, potentially process maturity.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges and objectives • Characteristics
(6) Participation	Explores factors for (group) involvement of vulnerable, including gender, location, the general openness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of vulnerable groups
(7) Information on the pro-nature activity	Looks at potential conflicts, (media) visibility, knowledge differences and balance, the initiative's broader societal change objectives, also its replicability and role model components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main outcomes • Characteristics

The type of information showcased in Table 1 was subsequently used to compile a comparative case analysis (see Section 3.1).

After selecting the relevant cases, we aimed to explore through specific interview questions *how* individuals become active, *what personal changes occur*, and how these actions *contribute to broader social and collective* change. This is operationalised through the lens of overlapping, intersectional vulnerabilities.

To understand all these aspects the following four main research questions were drawn up: **(1) personal motivations and moments of triggering for becoming active; (2) the participation process in relevant stewardship activities and its dynamics; (3) the role of knowledge for active participation; (4) the wider transformation** as personal or organisational change. In addition, we looked at the horizontal topic of **(5) vulnerabilities and gender specificities influencing behaviour.** (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Main RL2 research questions in the second research cycle.

The first research question addresses (A) **the motivation of vulnerable individuals and vulnerable groups**: What drives them to become active in environmental initiatives, and what factors trigger their involvement in pro-nature care activities? This question focuses on the personal and contextual bound drivers that inspire and motivate people to engage with environmental action, particularly those where livelihoods depend in many aspects on the natural resources in their environment, with livelihood we mean also recreation activities as spending time in nature for enjoyment.

The second question looks (B) at **group dynamics and the importance of roles**: How does participation in initiatives work, and why is it essential for individuals to engage as part of a group and finally take on specific roles? The emphasis extends to get more insights how joint activities trigger, contribute to collective behavioural change, especially among vulnerable groups, where collective action can amplify individual efforts. Notably is as well who is actually not included, left out for some reasons.

The third question (C) looks for evidence and explanations on **the role of knowledge** in environmental stewardship along our 11 cases: What kind of knowledge enables people to participate, and how is this knowledge accessed, shared, or tied to specific roles within communities? This question is central to understanding how information flows within groups and communities and how it empowers people to take meaningful action for nature. We consider the maturity of knowledge sharing as important, still limits occur for specialized knowledge.

The fourth and final question (D) explores **the potential for fundamental transformative change**: Can we observe such changes related to active individuals or groups? This considers whether participation in environmental initiatives leads to deeper, long-lasting shifts in behaviour or (new) societal norms, either on a personal or collective level see: (Laininen, 2019).

The **gender-specific factors** (E) are an overarching, horizontal topic. These include how gender influences motivations, participation and roles within groups, knowledge aspects, concerning transformative change (All from A to D).

The research questions were targeted at two distinct but related target groups, both relevant to gain insights for RL2, i.e. **organisers** and **participants**.

The **first group (organisers)** includes active, often highly networked persons who take on roles such as facilitators, leaders or experts. The key persons are acting as promoters or actively contribute to *all kinds of activities* within the cases. They occur to have a central role either in the processes of initiatives with an *unofficial designation* or they are *officially and formally designated* to prepare or guide activities. This group of “organisers” typically has specialised knowledge, such as legal or technical expertise. Our assumption is that they play a crucial role in co-developing activities as a wider group, and especially in the process of *including the second group* of “participants” in selected activities.

The **second group (participants)** contributes regularly to various activities of initiatives, are engaged in actions such as protest walks, or in practical tasks, e.g. maintaining landscape. They do rather *not take on* formal leadership assignments, and most importantly, their participation is *indispensable across all our RL2 cases*. They provide necessary *power for the success* of environmental initiatives. Participants relate more to *immediate action*, often acting directly along pro-nature issues that are relevant for their daily lives.

We assume that the group of “organisers” actively aims to involve more vulnerable citizens so they can act as intermediaries between vulnerable participants and public bodies or external stakeholders. Activities are co-developed by both groups but in many instances the coordination of specialised contributions supported by the “organisers” determines the outreach (and inclusive involvement of all groups) and thus influences the (behavioural) outcomes and impact of the initiatives.

To *incorporate reflected viewpoints*, RL2 decided to address **both groups with tailored questions**. In the interviews we used specific sets of questions for both groups, with the exception of the area of questions addressing *transformative change*. In this area we used the same set of interview questions for both groups, this would potentially allow us to capture potential differences and perspectives.

This approach allowed the researchers to capture distinct perspectives on pro-nature processes, behavioural change and transformative change. A reflective viewpoint emerges from accumulated experience stemming from similar/past initiatives, for instance from understanding legal frameworks, regulatory processes, know-how for stakeholder management and the necessary partnerships, policy impacts, long-term sustainability.

Having both groups interviewed in all 11 case studies opens up specific opportunities to add layers of complexity in understanding individual and group behavioural change, and enabling more insights in wider transformation processes. A perfect distinction for the two separate groups is not possible so our working assumptions remain experimental. In practice, responses sometimes *revealed a fluid, gradual distinction between the two groups* rather than a strict division, indicating a “natural” overlap in roles.

The core questions guiding RL2 research have been embedded in the two different semi-structured interview questionnaires. The research team prepared a complementary set of questions addressing the differentiated groups relevant within our initiatives, “organisers” and “participants”. To demonstrate practically how we followed this approach we present below the main differences of our interview characteristics (differences in questions) in a few paragraphs, concluded with an overview table.

Two differently shaped sets of questions address our first question, focusing on the *motivations to participate and triggers* to become involved. Differentiated questions for organisers and participants were elaborated to understand how citizens explain their motivation for active pro-nature action, to understand what triggers their engagement. Presumably, the synergetic interplay of both groups contributes to change. Practically, we combine the more on direct action-oriented explanations of participants with *partly* more reflected perspectives of organisers.

The **questions to participants** relate gradually more to a personal, experience-based perspective, they capture the personal perspective on pro-nature engagement. Participants were asked to share personal experiences and special conditions that *sparked* their environmental commitment. Participants' questionnaires focus on specific conditions that *lead individuals to engage* where we captured the *triggers* for personal behavioural change and how *individual motivations* have altered over time, or are *sustained* when achievements become evident.

Practically we relate in our interview questionnaires **to specific life events, new challenges, or changes in how one sees the world, also to special value positions**. In that way we highlight **intrinsic motivators** as emotional link to nature; existing individual and community values; wider personal positions on environmental issues, which contribute to “drive” behavioural change at an individual level. As we centred our research in RL2 on special initiatives and practical activities of pro-nature care, achievements within the initiative and personal impact were addressed as well. Individual motivations and links of personal reflections to achievements provide insights how behavioural change – for our specific question of motivation and triggers – *unfolds over time*.

The **questions to organisers** follow a reflective and strategic perspective, focusing on goal setting and mission. The questions motivate organisers to explain their personal motivation but also give information on the *wider drivers within their initiative*, the general motivation of acting as an initiative. Organisers were also asked to reflect their past experiences with pro-nature activities. This relates *both* to personal engagement (track of the past) and the *evolution of the initiative's mission over time*.

This perspective captures how behavioural changes (and changed approaches) occur at an *organisational level*, as many of our cases are shaped over time as cumulative experiences, including strategic shifts, also operationalising insights as responses to (new) *external pressures*. RL2 had the ambition to capture motivation *and inclusivity*, accessibility, offering reflected insights what enables citizen engagement in the initiative.

Table 2. Core aspects of the questions asked from the two main interview groups.

Core areas covered in interviews:	Collected information in interviews with participants	Collected information in interviews with organisers
Motivation and triggers	Personal experience and special conditions determining the own motivation to contribute pro-nature and also pointing to special events. Collecting participant's views on achievements.	Goal setting, mission and own role in the initiative. Experiences in the past and how the work of the initiative has changed. Reflective viewpoints on what motivates citizens to participate and how open and inclusive an initiative acts, who was/not included.
Participation	Personal reflection of joining the group of active citizens, emotional components, roles and the perception of openness to	Role of the group engagement, participation limits for participants and why citizens despite hesitation finally contribute.

	participate. Recalling what changes, the participation in the group for a person.	Reflection of how open the initiative is, what roles and responsibilities have further developed within the group.
Knowledge	Reference to information sources, traditional knowledge, specialized information and special knowledge contributors in the initiative.	Reflection on information sources and knowledge of participants, the relative importance of types of knowledge and accessibility of special knowledge. Knowledge attribution to supporters and transfer processes of knowledge.
Transformation	(identical information collected) Special signals of the initiative to society; main change of everyday practice and behaviour and readiness to contribute to new upcoming challenges	(identical information collected) Special signals of the initiative to society; main change of everyday practice and behaviour and readiness to contribute to new upcoming challenges

Finally, a few paragraphs about our data limitations. **Well-networked organisers within the initiatives played a crucial role as “door openers”** to identify members of both interview groups. Their involvement was irreplaceable: they were *helping filter, access and motivate participants*. They supported the research team to access a group of interviewees and conduct interviews within relatively short time. Relying on these central door openers **might have limited our outreach**. This means that a broader range of perspectives through a wider variety of cases might exist. The researchers acknowledge that *many more* initiatives exist that remain unknown to us, and they would have added as well significantly to this work.

In addition, our research focus relates to “participation aspects” and therefore it focuses on **social and group behaviour**. Collective action and group dynamics are interesting, and a special dynamic occurs in group settings, we try to focus *equally* on individual forms of pro-nature engagement. We are unsure if individual action of enthusiastic people acting beyond a certain group might in all cases be adequately covered.

We underline that the research team **does not aim to assess or compare different approaches used in cases, nor does it compare the involved groups**. The main aim is to understand and explain how changes of practice happen, how behavioural change appears in our RL2 focus area. Changes concern individuals, relevant groups involved in the variety of processes that are determining stewardship for nature.

An additional limitation of our research is that it does not explore in detail the specific role of public administrations in driving (or hindering) behavioural change by incorporating their perspectives and opinions directly. We do **not assess the effectiveness of current governance or administrative actors** in addressing environment, or more generally sustainability, we acknowledge the importance of these broader contexts.

Collected data and analysis

3. Collected data

3.1. Case description

All the cases relate to rural situations (with an urban pro-nature example included) and mainly in areas closely connected to neighbourhoods where the relationship to local living and livelihoods is

significant. Across these cases, citizens – whether observing or actively contributing – engage in various activities led by *both* formal and more informal groups.

There is a gradual variation in the *maturity* of these situations we describe as cases, with some demonstrating successful results of the initiatives, significant achievements, materialised or intangible results, such as changing mindsets and behaviours, while others are newer and not yet mature movements, formed recently and possess a certain *urgency* to counter imminent environmental threats with both impacting people’s life and valuable pieces of nature.

Table 3 is the reference point for the case descriptions in the analytical part of the RL2 report. It captures the geographical location and country; the main objectives of the pro-nature activities, present vulnerable groups and their characteristics; it summarises the main outcomes and gives general factors for outcomes along the main characteristics of the cases.

Table 3. Overview of interventions involved in cases selected by the RL2 team for RC2.

Short identifier	Geographical outreach	Challenges and objectives, framing activities	Vulnerable groups	Role of vulnerable groups	Main outcomes	Outcome factors	Characteristics
BG1: Gornoslav	Local, municipality	Opposing the development of a quarry at the UNESCO site, close to the village to protect environment and livelihood	Rural setting, including elderly but also young families moved to the place	Actively involved in many aspects, also, bound to place due to housing	The movement against the quarry development, including all villagers, elderly also were active. This intensified the village interactions. Now many see the need for a sustainable lifestyle or understand the need to change the situation, also beyond the village	Economic concerns, aging population, small pensions, high mobility costs. Income dependency on developer and administration.	Inclusive movement, good information access, and strong local networks. The rural lifestyle and shared values are central.
BG2: Pavlikeni - Varbovka	Local, municipality	Stopping construction of an incineration factory harmful to environment and health.	Roma community, marginalized groups	Informed and involved through outreach, collective action. Supported by diaspora remittances.	Inclusion of Roma community in protests, growing cohesion across the municipality, awareness raised on broader environmental issues.	Active outreach and information-sharing, legal activism, connections to past local movements, empowered community members.	Strong local leadership, legal expertise, and external support.

HU1: Bátya	Water catchment area	Floodplain rehabilitation to manage floods and restore habitat.	Local residents from marginalized area	Consultation role, caretaking actions within water catchment forum	Increased awareness of climate change mitigation and small-scale ecological actions.	Intrinsic motivation, climate impact concerns, financial incentives for landowners.	Resource planning at catchment level, availability of expertise and public lands.
Short identifier	Geographical outreach	Challenges and objectives, framing the activities	Vulnerable groups	Role of vulnerable groups	Main outcomes	Outcome factors	Characteristics
HU2: Püspökszilágy	Water catchment areas	Natural water management to mitigate floods, flash floods, and unbalanced water levels.	Local people in marginalized areas	Consultation role in the water catchment forum, caretaking actions	Floodplain rehabilitation, local organic farming and community education on sustainable practices.	Ecological and financial motivation, contribution to circular economy, nostalgic connection to former natural status.	Interlinked water retention measures, availability of public/private lands for organic farming.
HU3: Tiszatarján	Local village	Floodplain restoration, water retention, and land rehabilitation for economic purposes.	Roma minority, local people	Public workers involved in biomass production and water retention tasks	Floodplain restoration, reintroduction of native species, and energy independence for the municipality.	Ecological restoration, financial motivation (biomass production), skills acquisition.	Clear land tenure rules, access to resources (equipment, financial, human).

PT1: Bela Flor Respira	Local (Campolide , Lisbon)	Transform degraded space into agroforestry and involve local residents in food production.	Low-income people, elderly, immigrants, women	Planting, cultivating, community engagement, skill transfer	Raised environmental awareness, empowered community action, fostered sustainable consumption and intergenerational knowledge exchange.	Social and economic context, funding availability, cultural connections to nature, emotional benefits.	Local involvement, leadership, strong emotional connection to agriculture, hands-on learning environments.
Short identifier	Geographical outreach	Challenges and objectives, framing the activities	Vulnerable groups	Role of vulnerable groups	Main outcomes	Outcome factors	Characteristics
PT2: Natura Observa	Local/Regional (Sintra Cascais Natural Park)	Engage citizens in biodiversity conservation through active participation in environmental monitoring.	Some low-income participants	Volunteers perform habitat restoration, species monitoring, and environmental education tasks	Increased environmental awareness, adoption of sustainable practices, and community involvement in broader conservation efforts.	Personal background, values, hands-on learning, emotional connection to nature, group solidarity.	Adaptation to local social, cultural, and environmental context. Emotional engagement and local leadership are key.
RO1: Mountain Garbage Dump Mestecaniş Mountain	Local, nationally popularized	Stopping landfill development with European funding, overcoming local political interests.	Elderly, people with disabilities, low-income groups	Mobilizing residents, solidarity-building, active participation	Temporary project stoppage, increased community cohesion, systematic protests.	Legal actions, protecting local traditions and biological products, mass media pressure.	Media partnerships, political transparency, willingness to act for common goals.

RO2: Protecting Biodiversity Bucovina	Local	Protecting biodiversity and restoring balance in deforested areas despite fear and lack of support.	Elderly, people partly with disabilities, low-income groups	Specialists, educators, support role	Restoration of natural balance, reforestation, maintaining control of local species	Love for nature, education, specialized knowledge, personal experience	Limited due to the need for practical knowledge, time availability, and individual willingness to engage.
Short identifier	Geographical outreach	Challenges and objectives, framing the activities	Vulnerable groups	Role of vulnerable groups	Main outcomes	Outcome factors	Characteristics
TK1: Sarikecililer Nomads	Local and regional, with brief national outreach	Defending nomads' grazing rights against state policies restricting movement.	Nomads, women, educational challenges	Led by vulnerable groups, conducting outreach, administration, and education	Legal changes allowing goat grazing, increased self-confidence, environmental awareness.	Strong leadership, deep connection to nature, networks with other ecological movements, communal independence.	Contribution of goat grazing to forest fire prevention, strong communal traditions, public awareness of indigenous knowledge.
TK2: Akbelen Forest	Local, now national	Stopping coal mine operation encroaching on forests and villages, resisting state-supported destruction.	Small-scale farmers, forest villagers, women with limited mobility	Led by vulnerable groups, involved in networking and education	Empowerment of women as movement leaders, greater awareness of environmental-political connections.	Geographical importance, women's leadership, health issues due to mine pollution, early collaboration with environmental movements.	Networking experience, strong public frustrations with forest destruction, connections with broader environmental and social movements.

In **Bulgaria**, two distinct methods were used to identify active pro-nature initiatives. For the **first case**, a long-standing contact with a prominent ecological organisation informed the researcher about an active pro-nature initiative in a village in southern Bulgaria, located close to an UNESCO-protected natural area. The village faces environmental challenges due to a regional company's plans to activate a limestone quarry. After a preliminary visit to gather initial insights, a second visit was necessary to conduct interviews with participants and organisers involved in the important local initiative. Key concerns in this case revolve around regional business activities prioritising profit over sustainability and disregarding the impact on residents' livelihoods. Vulnerabilities in this rural area primarily relate to age, socio-economic challenges, and partly to geographic distance to more developed regional centres.

The **second case** in central Bulgaria was introduced to the active researchers by local activists and combines pro-nature and environmental activities. This initiative addresses administrative shortcomings in ecological protection, particularly surrounding a glass wool production facility known to exploit nearby resources and its plans to engage in unsafe waste incineration practices with devastating environmental impact, the release e.g. of Furans (Dioxine) and many more negative effects. The movement here includes a nearby Roma community, whose proximity to the factory adds urgency to their involvement. Two pre-visits were needed to build trust and ensure community participation, particularly among ethnic minorities.

Both Bulgarian initiatives are self-funded, strictly adhere to legal frameworks, and are driven by locals aiming to protect their livelihoods while promoting sustainability. Building trust was crucial in both cases, supported by translated materials on the project, informed consent, and ethical procedures approved by the Ethics Commission at ZSI.

In **Hungary**, recruitment for interviews for the **three case studies** relates to projects funded by European and national programmes. The three case studies are similar in their geographical location and their socio-economic context. All three cases are in water catchment areas confronted with dangers such as flash floods, drought or degradation. Villages are within marginalised sub-regions of Hungary that are confronted with multiple vulnerability issues, e.g. unemployment, missing resources or sub-sufficient infrastructure. Vulnerable communities are involved in pro-nature activities of **previous LIFE-funded projects**. One case was also involved in the first ACCTING research cycle. Support from local municipality enabled the recruitment. For the two new cases, the interviewer coordinated with the mayors. To build trust and act according to ethic requirements of ZSI, the informed consent was translated to Hungarian language. During the interviews the interviewer informed as well on opt-out option. A challenge were the timely close municipal elections. Also contacts to national organisations were available but remained on standby and were ultimately not needed.

In **Portugal**, the recruitment process for interviews involved tailored approaches. In the **first case**, **Bela Flor Respira** (agroforestry project in Lisbon), participants were invited based on their volunteer engagement and residency in the Bela Flor neighbourhood. The researchers collaborated with the Campolide Parish Council and a former community facilitator to access participants. Recruitment was challenging, with many participants not responding to initial outreach. Researchers provided a brief invitation, established informed consent and provided more information once interviews were scheduled. Reminder messages and flexible rescheduling options were offered to accommodate participants' schedules. The process was further complicated by funding cuts of the project, which reduced volunteer engagement. This development made recruitment a challenging process.

In the **second case**, **Natura Observa** (a volunteer programme in the Sintra-Cascais Natural Park), recruitment was supported by a coordinator from Ambiente Cascais, the municipal company

overseeing the programme. Researchers made multiple visits to volunteer teams, introduced the ACCTING project, and invited collaboration from volunteers and team leaders. Additionally, prior to the youth campaign, the team contacted local schools and the Cascais scouts via e-mail and phone to expand the participant pool, especially among vulnerable groups. Still, the response was limited.

Notably, the Campolide Parish Council and Ambiente Cascais were already familiar with the ACCTING project from the first research cycle, having previously collaborated within Research Line 5, which facilitated trust and openness in participant recruitment. All participants in the study were provided with informed consent, which detailed the project's name, objectives, their selection as participants, confidentiality and anonymity provisions, and confirmation of no risks involved. To establish trust, interviewers visited benefiting areas, engaged in informal conversations during fieldwork, and introduced the ACCTING project through local organisations, promoters, and partners of the initiatives.

In **Romania**, recruitment for interviews in the two case studies was set up to engage both organisers and participants as interview partners. In **case 1, Mestecaniş Mountain landfill protests**, recruitment focused on residents and activists involved in actions against the landfill project. Respected contacts in Suceava County helped identify those who had engaged in protests, petitions, and legal actions aimed at preserving the region's natural beauty.

In **case 2, in Bucovina addressing conservation efforts**, participants included locals involved in biodiversity protection, with recruitment facilitated through personal contacts to community members active in reforestation and wildlife monitoring. Trust-building was key, with researchers providing clear information and procedures of confidentiality and openly informing about the ACCTING project goals and affiliations. Some participants hesitated to discuss sensitive topics like illegal logging. All participants received informed consent forms in Romanian language, detailed project information, information about the rationale for their involvement and confidentiality information. To enable a trusted relationship the researcher held informal conversations, followed up with flexible scheduling for interviews. Vulnerabilities were especially evident among older participants with low pensions or physical disabilities, reflecting that the community context was also marked by traditional gender roles. Limitations included the overall small pool of participants, low educational attainment, and difficulty reaching some key door openers, such as a wildlife monitoring expert. Despite these challenges, the sample offers a broad spectrum of perspectives, and provides valuable insights into community pro-nature developments.

In **Türkiye**, recruitment for interviews relates to two distinct case studies including mostly personal fights, community struggles and in a setting of unique environmental and social challenges. In **case 1, the Sarıkeçililer Nomadic Community**, recruitment focused on members of the traditional pastoralist community, their way of life significantly contributing to biodiversity but also related to political pressures on the community. The community's nomadic lifestyle is increasingly threatened by state policies and encouraging settlement in towns, public misconceptions, restrictions of grazing routes, specific forestry policies, and climate impacts on the nomadic lifestyle. For research purposes, the research team collaborated closely with the Sarıkeçililer Solidarity Association, founded in 2012 to advocate for grazing, other community rights. Initial contacts were difficult, as the community expressed its hesitancy toward external research. Regular engagement with the community and ongoing contact with the association provided continuity and insights over more than a year. By approaching a door-opener, a trusted key community representative and a meeting in a local, neutral location, trust was (gradually) established. This approach allowed the community to maintain self-control over the process, facilitating six interviews, two with women and four with men.

In **case 2, the Akbelen Forest** struggle, recruitment centred on members of KARDOK (Karadam Karacahisar Neighbours Association for the Protection, Beautification, and Solidarity of Nature and Natural Life), an organization formed in 2020 to protect the forest from encroaching mining activities. Akbelen Forest, located in Milas, is one of the few remaining green spaces in a region heavily impacted by mining and deforestation. Villagers, some of whom had relocated to urban areas only to face precarious conditions, returned to defend their community and environment. Over 2.5 years, the SU researchers established connections through a respected activist involved in the initiative. Interviews were conducted with key organisers, mostly women, who took leading roles despite facing significant pressures. Given the sensitivity of the situation, interviewees were assured anonymity, and their narratives will not be published in the ACCTING database.

3.2. Sample description and vulnerability factors

RL2 included 11 cases, with results based on a **sample of 35 women and 36 men interviewees**. The sample has additional differentiations, as previously described, highlighting two groups of varying significance within the initiatives, **organisers and participants**.

- In total, **20 organisers** were interviewed, consisting of **11 woman and 9 men**, with case-specific differentiation ranging from **one to four organisers in a case**.
- The group of interviewed **participants** includes **51 individuals – 24 women and 27 men** with a number per case varying from **two to eight participants**.
- Across countries, each RL2 partner conducted between 10 and 17 interviews covering between two to three cases.

Of our 11 cases, **five feature more men interviewees**, while **six include more women interviewees**.

- Regarding roles, **six** cases have only women organisers, **four** only men, and one case includes **both men and women** organisers.
- Among participants, there is a general balance between men and women contributors.

Table 4. Quantitative overview of numbers of cases, interview partners of both groups per covered country.

Country	cases on territory	Organisers		Participants		All interviews		% of women	TOTAL
		women	men	women	men	women	men		
Bulgaria	2	3	4	4	5	7	9	43,8%	16
Hungary	3	3	3	2	4	5	7	41,7%	12
Portugal	2	3	0	8	6	11	6	64,7%	17
Romania	2	0	2	7	7	7	9	43,8%	16
Türkiye	2	2	0	3	5	5	5	50,0%	10
Total:	11	11	9	24	27	35	36	49,3%	71

Each RL2 partner systematically gathered **standardised information on subjective inequalities** experienced by interviewees for both groups. This context-bound information describes also inequalities that influence the experiences of both participants and organisers within the initiatives. The subjective inequalities, as documented during interviews, and split in the two groups are as follows:

Table 5. Subjective inequalities in the RL2 sample (order as collected) and differentiating in the two interview groups.

Subjective inequality	Participants	Importance amongst participants	Organisers	Importance amongst organisers	Total	Importance overall
Not applicable	3	15%	1	2%	4	6%
No subjective inequality	4	20%	14	27%	18	25%
Gender	4	20%	3	6%	7	10%
LGBTQ+ status	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Age	2	10%	7	14%	9	13%
Disability	1	5%	2	4%	3	4%
Nationality and/or migrant status	0	0%	4	8%	4	6%
Religion/belief	1	5%	0	0%	1	1%
Language	0	0%	1	2%	1	1%
Ethnic, racial, and/or social origin	3	15%	6	12%	9	13%
Social class/socioeconomic background	4	20%	23	45%	27	38%
Geographic location	11	55%	26	51%	37	52%
Other	0	0%	1	2%	1	1%

The main subjective inequalities relate to the geographic location as the RL2 team covers in 71 interviews mostly **rural areas** that correspond to this factor. Closely linked to this situation is the second prominent inequality, **social class/socioeconomic background**. Finally we find **social**

origin, age and other factors including gender as important in our sample. In the following we present an overview of inequalities met in the different participating countries. Below, we provide an overview of the **inequalities encountered across the different participating countries**:

Table 6. Subjective inequalities in the RL2 sample (order as collected) and highlighting inequalities with more than 2 mentions.

Subjective Inequality	Bulgaria	Hungary	Portugal	Romania	Türkiye
Not applicable*	2	0	1	1	0
No subjective inequality*	0	0	10	7	1
Gender	0	3	0	0	4
LGBTQ+ status	0	0	0	0	0
Age	2	3	0	3	1
Disability	2	0	0	1	0
Nationality and/or migrant status	0	1	3	0	0
Religion/belief	1	0	0	0	0
Language	0	0	1	0	0
Ethnic, racial, and/or social origin	6	1	0	0	2
Social class/socioeconomic background	8	1	6	3	9
Geographic location	12	12	3	2	8
Other	0	0	1	0	0

Enablers and hindrances in our sample

Each RL2 partner systematically collected standardised information for individual resources with roles as enablers or hindrances. This context-specific information are the factors that either support or hinder the engagement of participants and organisers for the initiatives. Presented graphically, the enablers and hindrances give an impression of a diverse, context-dependent variety that reflects the unique circumstances of each case. Many of the interviewees expressed the lack of time and financial resources as the main hindrances, followed and pronounced (by all but not the Hungarian cases) is the access to political and social actors. Most pronounced enabler is knowledge, followed by education and the perceived self-efficacy.

Figure 3. Individual resources as enablers and hindrances in our sample.

Each RL2 partner has also systematically collected standardised information on social dynamics influencing participation in the initiatives, and their role as enablers or hindrances for both participants and organisers. Many of the initiatives highlight the strong role of community and social networks as core enablers of engagement, though with a wide variety of expressions. This context-specific data underscores the importance of relationships – also a highlighted enabling factor. Shared beliefs and values, feelings of social appreciation are shaping participation. Obstructive, hindering components were differentiated less pronounced, with the exception of Romanian cases where the social appreciation stands out as a core hindrance in this category.

Figure 4. Social Dynamics as enablers and hindrances in our sample.

Each RL2 partner gathered data on structural condition as factors that influence participation in the initiatives. Most structural conditions, particularly in the RL2 rural areas and location-specific initiatives, are challenging to quantify due to their context-dependent nature. Unique conditions influence the relevance of structural enablers and hindrances differently. The geographical location and environment are considered as enablers, whereas other enablers appear here rather case-specific but not highlighted by a majority of cases.

Hindrances related to our interviewees relate strongly to social- and economic conditions, to policies and politics. This relates strongly to our sample of cases that consists of many action-oriented movements that try to find ways of stopping potentially destructive changes of environment or strong impacts on the (rural) livelihood.

Figure 5. Structural conditions as enablers and hindrances in our sample.

3.3. Analysis

3.3.1. Change and impact within and across countries

Common insights and overview of findings: Research on “Motivations and

triggers”

Our **first core question** addresses the **motivations and triggers** for engaging in pro-nature activities. We seek to understand what drives individuals to actively care for nature, their immediate surroundings.

Our findings highlight that participants’ as well as organiser’s primary concerns relate more to their living conditions or the dangers associated with their place of residence than to a purely intrinsic motivation to protect or conserve a wild nature, important habitats of animals or specific species. Many interviewees were motivated to contribute to pro-nature activities as they appeared interconnected with neighbourhood quality, essential ecosystem services related to the living place (i.e. rural village), and an environment deemed integral or inseparable from the community life and survival (most dramatic in the case of nomadic pastoralism in TK1).

For all the 11 initiatives, we observe a strong **livelihood** perspective, relating to local struggles for a liveable environment that integrates nature. Across the various cases, a common thread in motivations and triggers for engaging in pro-nature activities are rooted in a **blend of personal and community concerns**. Interviewees express that their commitment to protecting the environment is closely linked to the quality of life within their communities and the (expected or in reality) impact of local environmental changes on daily life.

Many participants express that their **sense of duty** to act pro-nature relates to direct experiences with local (or closely to the living places) environmental issues that impact their immediate living conditions. For example, concerns such as pollution, access to clean water, accessible forest or meadows for grazing, and the preservation (or build up) of green spaces are seen as essential for supporting the quality of life in a rural setting.

Many people view nature not as a **separate entity but also as an integral part of the community fabric** – essential to health, well-being, and social cohesion. We see this for example in case **BG1**, an initiative against a quarry close to the village. The situation is highlighted from a village perspective and the expected impact on the livelihood. Noise, dust, water shortage as expected impacts of mining are discussed, also the role of wells for the surrounding five villages is reflected. This relates to the special ecosystem services and contribution of nature to people’s life as an important point for the respondent. The interviewee also points to the tradition of planting trees in the green belt above the village where in the past mining activities have been unavoidable.

“Who lives here takes care of the resources and nature, we have a strong interest to keep our surrounding intact for us and all our next generations that will live here.” (BG1, R5, P)

In the case of **TK1** Sarıkeçililer Nomadic Community, the nomadic pastoralists that bridge in their pastoralism a distance of up to 350 km during spring, another explanation was found, that bridges to the natural environment and the way of living and survival. One of our interviewees expressed the living within nature without differentiating the forest from the own being constantly with “we” and showing the strong interconnectedness:

“We live in harmony with nature. If there were no forest in nature, we wouldn’t exist. If we didn’t exist, the forest wouldn’t be there either. So, the forest is very valuable to us.”(TK1, R5, P)

In **PT1** one of the organisers informed that there is a complex interplay that motivates people to engage in pro-nature care activities. She relates this to community dynamic and the observation that a wide interplay exists, which also can start from the wider people’s needs.

"I have a role in the Agroforestry project in the sense that it is in a phase of sustainability...we are trying to understand what the population needs from the parish council so that the agroforestry can continue to play an important role there in the Bela Flor neighbourhood"(PT1, R1, O)

Across both groups of participants and organisers, a **shared sense of ownership** and responsibility towards their natural surroundings is evident. Interviewees commonly view pro-nature activities as deeply embedded in the social fabric – even extended to their herds of sheep - where **local struggles for a sustainable environment become acts of preserving heritage and, community identity**.

We find in our cases that this relationship is constantly reinforced through the participation in activities, it is seen as a single chance of becoming active. These efforts of pro-nature activities, many of the participants find a purpose not only in contributing to environmental protection but also in supporting the **cohesion and survival of their community** (leaving it here open what exactly one considers as her/his community).

By contrast, the pro-nature engagement is not always seen positively. In RO2, for instance, one interviewee refers to waste deposit by local inhabitants from his village. Though he observes this behaviour regularly, he has no power to change it. He expresses this destructive behaviour with many frustrations as follows:

"They shouldn't throw so much garbage in the forest, that's a ravage and a devastation, they bring garbage from the house and go to the forest to throw it away. They do this because of lack of education. I have an obsession with this and stop anyone I catch doing it. I ask them, do you do the same in other countries when you go? And they answer me, well no, that the fines are high there. I then tell them to collect immediately that I will notify the authorities and take them on the spot because they are scared. A lot of people advise me to leave them alone because that's how I make enemies. They ask me who am I to tell them what to do?" (RO2, R5, P)

A sense of **responsibility toward future generations** emerges as another core motivator for engaging in pro-nature activities. Intergenerational **justice** consistently appears as explanatory narrative across cases.

The commitment to preserving nature and its vital resources underscores the importance of leaving a healthy environment for those who come after (see also Scopelliti et al., 2022).

In RO1, one respondent addresses this very clearly and with a reference to intergenerational justice to the ancestors and the future generation as follows:

"[...]I can also add that I would not be able to look in the mirror if I did not get involved in this kind of actions, it is a moral duty to our ancestors and to future generations." (RO1, R4, P)

Furthermore, motivations and triggers for dedicated pro-nature involvement reveal the significant role of **emotional connections** in driving action. These motivations are shaped by personal experiences, cultural backgrounds, lifestyles, and community dynamics. Emotional bonds often span generations, rooted in memories of past homes, or evoking feelings of frustration and helplessness when, as one interviewee expressed, *"there is nowhere else to go."* Frustrating encounters with ineffective administration, a sluggish political system, disconnected from people's needs, repressive political conditions and difficult socio-economic realities convince citizens to become active for a liveable future. Initially, our questions centred on individual behavioural change, but responses reveal explanations, narratives of how people decided to act, referring to past experiences, unsatisfactory developments, or other situations that inspired a community-based spirit of self-reliance and solidarity as well.

In case TK2, the struggle to protect the Akbelen forest from the mining destruction, one interviewee emphasises the emotional aspects of the struggle together with the intergenerational family bonds to nature, and links this with the emotions of past of much hope and integration of many life aspects as follows:

"Our life was much better before. Why was it better? Because we had our forests. In the forest, we had our birds, wolves, insects—everything. We had our flowers, fruits—everything. My future source was my forest. When my children came home from school, they would go to the forest with their grandmother, with the goats and the sheep. I would look after all of them together. How beautiful it was to pick flowers; I would make crowns from daisies." (TK2, R3, P)

Emotional bonds and the deep sense of loss following the struggle's defeat express the connection to place, known since the birth, its traditions, and the significant events that have impacted nature and the people living since generations in the area. These powerful emotions look backwards and reflect on the destruction of livelihoods sustained over generations.

The following excerpt captures the intense struggle, a (lost) fight against the destruction of nature, driven by bonds that determined and motivated the resistance at every step.

"It's a huge wound for us to have lost this place. Leaving behind the land of one's birth, the home where one grew up, or even demolishing it with one's own hands. Now, you go there. It's as if there's nothing left. Suddenly, it's like a cliff. Excavators have dug it out, and the other side is not visible. You look and see that the bottom is truly not visible; it's a cliff. Seeing the destruction of the village step by step is something entirely different...." (TK2, R1, O)

Role models for the engagement and motivation to act pro-nature, along with intergenerational exchange as an "authority" for integrating the pro-nature behaviour into daily life, were included in the collected explanations. This inspiration and motivation connects to the role of knowledge—both as it is interwoven into the lives of interviewees and as it continues through traditional land use practices.

The Bela Flor Respira agroforest initiative (PT1) creates a better balanced nature by targeted human pro-nature action. Here we refer to **intergenerational inspiration** that influences motivation, serves as a personal catalyst. The rooted intergenerational inspiration triggers active participants to develop a strong interest in sustainable practices.

"I can't say exactly when it started... my grandparents had a garden, my parents had a garden, the connection with the land was always strong... and then trying to see how we could improve, improve organic agriculture, with agroforestry, so we've already introduced some trees also in my parents' garden, then I started doing more training, in the last 5/6 years, there were more trainings, I was involved in several groups, associations, spread across Portugal, the most important ones, where they address agroforestry..." (PT1, R6, P)

We have observed in our RL2 cases that one motivation for citizens to step into pro-nature initiatives is the **ineffectiveness of administration and inadequate governance processes** that fail to address sustainability challenges related to nature. In several cases of RL2, there is suspicion that **administrations do not look on citizens' interests first**, instead showing a pro-business attitude. It is beyond our scope to determine the validity of this perception across our cases. Yet, it is clear that many decisions *rather ignore* the living conditions of people or the importance of nature in their daily lives. Similarly, institutions acting pro-business do not reflect on the *significance of nature itself in their daily governing practice* – in some instances we can exclude specialised units in charge of environment that co-develop with the initiatives and take on the messages in their daily operations.

We encountered *contradictory positions between different administrative bodies*. Such are exemplary local mayors and other administrative local actors, state institutions (exemplary regional ecological inspections), environment agencies or national branches of ministries as competent authorities act *inconsistent and work “against” each other*. Institutional roles, the inherent logics of administrations and diverging objectives - even in the supporting branches of the institutions - might still ignore or not consider citizens (and especially vulnerable groups). We consider that the ongoing social construction of frames of the initiatives/social movements is a key driver, also covered in the next research sub-question on participation.

Table 7. RL2 cases in light of: Temporality, dynamic, motivations/triggers and the role of administrations.

BG1: Gornoslav	Urgent: Quarry	Progressing but small wins	Livelihood impact Reference to past experience Safeguarding UNESCO protected area	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Business supportive ∅ pro-initiative (selected actors)
BG2: Pavlikeni (Varbovka)	Urgent: Incinerator	Progressing, specialised legal struggle is “away” from area	Livelihood impact Neglected role of inhabitants Citizen movement influencing non-citizen focus of administration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Business supportive
HU1: Bática	Ongoing flood land rehabilitation as project delivery	Project duration is limited, employment as participation, ownership challenge	Livelihood impact Financial (small) benefits Planned involvement in project	I Pro-environment
HU2: Püspökszilágy	Ongoing flood land and sustainable farming project delivery	Project duration is limited, employment as participation, ownership challenge	Livelihood impact Financial (small) benefits, midterm job creation Planned involvement in project	I Pro-environment
HU3: Tiszatarján	Ongoing flood land restoration as project delivery	Project duration is limited, employment as participation, ownership challenge	Livelihood impact Financial (small) and non-financial benefits Planned involvement in project	I Pro-environment
PT1: Bela Flor Respira	Ongoing rehabilitation towards agroforest	True long term engagement setting challenging needed	Livelihood impact Non-financial impact	I Pro-environment
PT2: Natura Observa	Ongoing volunteering programme	Multidimensional bundle of activities with incoming supporters	Intrinsic pro-nature actions Social interaction	I Pro-environment
RO1: Mountain Garbage Dump	Long struggle with achievements	Keeping up motivation after important achievements	Livelihood impact Continuing an enthusiastic past	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Business supportive (past) ∅ undecided (current time)

RO2: Protecting Biodiversity	Ongoing local restoration	Long term engagement challenge and subsistence living	Livelihood impact Tradition and resilience	∫ Absence of administration
TK1: Sarikecililer Nomads	Safeguarding nomadic living and their grazing areas	Important achievements for the groups' grazing rights	Maintaining lived practice, culture Tradition and group resilience Social cohesion of group	∫ Absence (mostly)
TK2: Akbelen Forest	Partially "lost" struggle for living area (mining)	Sustaining the attention of supporters	Livelihood impact Tradition and resilience	✘ Business supportive ✘ Criminalising protest

Legend: | ...administration pro-nature, supporting the initiative; ∅ rather undecided; ∫ Absence of administration; ✘ ...in opposition to initiative

Common insights and overview of findings: Participation

Our **second core question** looks on the explanations of behavioural change appearing from *collective group participation* in pro-nature care taking activities. The 11 pro-nature initiatives relate to engagement processes with a significant outreach component in the local community based on (or forming in the process) a **committed local community of practice**.

Differentiated roles emerge in this process, with subgroups forming around specific tasks, also the development of ownership within an initiative becomes an intriguing aspect. This multifaceted process varies across the local initiatives in RL2, with gradual differences in how leadership is expressed, the processes followed by all participants or specific organizing contributors, and especially important for ACCTING, how vulnerable groups are integrated into the collective pro-nature engagement.

Participation and the collective power of solidarity relate to all RL2 pro-nature movements. A closer view on the role and significance in people's lives uncovers why commitment can have different paces. Limited resources create barriers, often determining an individual's ability to fully commit. The group dynamics, often led by women and the social cohesion around environmental topics not only enable a direct involvement in specific cases but more long-lasting participatory processes. The previous chapter introduced earlier findings on individual motivations and triggers to become active. The received explanations also included the participation in a group as common goals were shared, *as trusted persons invited further persons* to participate to strengthen the power of the initiative, e.g. to have more signatories in a petition, to have more **collective power** for forest restoration, etc.

The appearance of a collective process is often a precondition that individual citizens can actually become active. Participation as a group in pro-nature action links to the actual group living in the area with certain collective community goals.

The recognition that acting as a group is essential to achieving place-based collective goals was frequently highlighted by interviewees as a main motivation to become active. Related to the above is the aspect of **solidarity**. Once a community exists with a certain practice, or a group of new practice *had been* formed, many participants felt a **sense of duty** to join, seeing becoming active as an act of solidarity and a demonstration of commitment to all residents within the village or area.

The power of solidarity and collective commitment is emphasised in our case **BG1**, the fight against a quarry close to the village is expressed as follows:

We are a community at the end of the day... One person can't stop a quarry because you're a nobody, but when we become 5, 10, 20, 70, 100, it's a completely different story. (BG1, R2, P)

Similarly, in **BG2**, this is expressed by those who cannot participate: *Some stay silent. But internally, they are in solidarity.* (BG2, R1, P)

In our interview in **PT2**, the Natura Observa initiative the collective physical work is the only way the activities can work out, so a part of the explanations why each one is valuable in the activity when taking out invasive species from a plot of land appears as a call for collective action: *"Meeting new people and working together, even if one person can't pull out an acacia by themselves, someone else helps, and it all works out. Teamwork is really important here..."* (PT2, R7, P).

We also find explanations about the **limits of participatory action**, which emphasises the personal responsibility vis-a-vis the group engagement, such as in case **RO1**, i.e. the struggle with the garbage landfill:

"I don't think that involvement at the group level is very important. I think it's important for everyone to do what they can, how they can, whenever they can, without necessarily being part of a specific group.

But I think that as you are taught at home, as a child, so you do, with or without a group. If you weren't taught from a young age to love nature, you're part of various groups for nothing, that it's equal to zero, you still don't realize much." (RO1, R1, P)

In **TK1**, the Sarikecililer Nomads, the physical distance of the community challenges the direct communication, and a strong connecting and networked, trusted person integrates the disbursed contributors. Priority is expressed by one interviewee putting family survival first, followed by the community goals and solidarity. Especially the solidarity against the **prejudice towards the nomads** – by settled villagers, administration, the general public resulting in restrictions of free moving with the herds – is seen as an obligation.

The process of destruction of a culture that carefully interacts with nature is described as an urgent call of being attentive and also continuing the community activities: *"At this rate, they'll destroy our culture. It used to exist in four main places, but now it's only left in the Toros Mountains. They're slowly erasing it, trying to settle us down."* (TK1, R2, P)

Also, the integrity of animals, **interspecies solidarity** is expressed in a unique way, explaining the own sustained and culturally embedded behaviour as follows: *"They [other people] don't have the courage. For example, if I hadn't had the courage to start animal husbandry, one day this would be left unattended. If I let it go, either wolves would tear it apart or it would break apart. It would disappear, meaning all the effort is tied to one day. But to bring it to this point takes years, days, months—it takes a lifetime chasing after this. This is how courage brings confidence."*(TK1, R2, P)

In the interviews we learnt about the many **intrinsic barriers hindering participation**. For instance, fear of revenge from the administration when one supports certain initiatives was expressed straight to the point in case BG2:

"People who depend on the mayor are afraid to participate because they could lose their jobs." (BG2, O, R2)

Another barrier is losing the **protective family environment** in a more publicly visible and probably less comfortable (safe) movement. It is fear of the unknown, an unfamiliar setting and potential discrimination. This was expressed in the volunteer-based **PT2** Natura Observa activities by an organiser as a *"comfort zone that people do not like to leave"*. Organisers actively overcome this in the **TK1**, the Sarikecililer Nomads, by identifying a well matching supporter for negotiating the grazing areas as expressed in this quote:

"If there is a meeting with a governor somewhere, I don't go alone. I say here, 'This is the situation; who is available? Let's have this person or that person go, auntie [elder sister] let's do this [...]" (TK1, R1, O)

In the PT2 initiative in Cascais, an organiser expresses the **fear of discrimination** as an intrinsic barrier as follows:

"Are they afraid of being discriminated against?" - "Yes, they are very afraid. But, for example, in Maré Viva, which is another project, they participate more because it's at the beach. [...] because it's in an area they already frequent, as it's both a neighbourhood and a beach." (PT2, R1, O)

There are many pathways to overcome such barriers. For instance, knowledge (in many dimensions) is considered an **important enabler in relation to the group participation and inclusive engagement**. In the three Hungarian cases we identified a planned, highly formalised engagement process. In **HU2**, the gradual process of steering community participation by providing tailor-made

opportunities is challenging, it relates to information and a **trust gaining process** with involving several actors, the organisers, children and finally their parents, to become engaged:

"We organised a blue - green village day in May where we inaugurated the educational trail and organised a quiz separate for children and adults. People were very enthusiastic, around 50-100 persons filled out the quiz for which they had to gather information about water and nature through the educational trail. We gave out valuable prizes, such as a chainsaw, a fishing rod and book voucher." (HU2, R1, O)

Continuous engagement activities are related to ownership, where a sense of belonging to the initiatives are established and thus intrinsic barriers are mitigated. For instance, in cases **PT1** and **PT2**, a systematic community building is undertaken with a rather complex empowerment goal, which includes the younger generation too:

"The project's objective was that the community could be the owner, so to speak, of the maintenance of that space...[...] It's also a space for socializing, that is, it combats social isolation, and I think that's fantastic. [...] We must be present in the neighbourhoods, work with the children who live in these neighbourhoods because they are the future". (PT1, R1, O).

Urgent pro-nature activities as participatory joint grassroots activities also appeared in some of our cases. They constitute **less formalised** participation processes and remain highly dynamic and flexible. Six cases involved in RL2 follow an agile and dynamic *engagement process*. They reach out to involve participants to **increase legitimacy, significance, visibility, strength** and develop their own flexible strategies in this process. They succeed to maintain a collective engagement through a bundle of different activities.

Such cases include **BG1, BG2, RO1**, partly **RO2**, and with a common determinant of traditional pro-nature action the community responses **TK1**, and **TK2**. The role of lead persons or more active coordinating groups is important. In our cases we see active women in the centre who contribute in key roles to the group dynamics and case development.

The explanations **why women took on those special roles** are related to the fact that traditional gender roles bind them to a specific area. They **protect the own livelihood as family organisers** or leaders of the **entire community**. The roles appear also from **special abilities** as expressed in **TK2**, the Akbelen Forest safeguarding efforts:

"When we go somewhere and give a speech or make a press statement about this place, we always want women to speak. Because they speak emotionally and express their feelings. They know what this place means and have no personal gain from it. Their only concern is to protect this place. We even asked the men to speak, but the men didn't do much. Since women are taking the lead and carrying it forward, it has become more their responsibility." (TK2, R1, O)

Common insights and overview of findings: Knowledge as enabler and hindrance

Our **third core question** looks for explanations for the role of knowledge in supporting pro-nature activities. This relates to case-specific context-bound conditions that *enable or hinder* pro-nature activities for environmental stewardship. The aim is to understand knowledge dynamics, the accessibility of knowledge resources, its sharing process and the way we can attribute knowledge sharing to specific roles-

One explanation for the importance and enabling role of knowledge is the observation that knowledge is a practical asset for functional (and impactful) work of all 11 RL2 initiatives. Several cases illustrate

the importance of **local knowledge in mobilising** local communities. In the context of the RL2 cases we define **different kinds of knowledge**, e.g. traditional, scientific, experiential, and collaboration (as described in the previous core question).

Traditional knowledge rooted in local culture serves as one of the foundations for pro-nature behaviour. The knowledge dynamic in our 11 cases is often gendered, with women and older members commonly seen as the “custodians” of cultural and ecological knowledge. For instance, **BG1** gives insights how knowledge of landscape use is becoming important as a resource for the current struggle.

Our grandparents took care of the land without destroying it. That’s what we need to continue. (BG1, P, R3)

This knowledge of the past is emphasised by participants. However, this relates to a historic image, a past in which not all of the active members of initiatives have been living. In short, it consists of narratives that can be rather historic than evidenced. A participant in **RO2** describes another perspective that avoids this perspective of traditions and refers to missing pieces of information about environmental impacts of the own neighbourhood as follows:

“I would rather refer to the practices in the area, not the traditions. For example, there are no sewers everywhere in the area, there are many clarifiers today that pollute the water table tremendously because of the detergents. This is a very serious thing, because when you send the water for analysis, everyone analyses bacteria, nitrites, nitrates, but what comes from the detergents and seeps into the soil, I have not heard of anyone checking. Every house has at least one decanter, do you realize that the water table is a disaster?!” (RO2, P, R1)

RO1 highlights **intergenerational knowledge transmission**, with elderly locals passing on knowledge of small-scale farming and livestock care as practical means of pro-nature acting to next generations. One person was adding a controversial viewpoint of how traditional knowledge along land use is not a valid solution in the current situation:

“Every social custom or tradition has a role and is harmoniously integrated into our human activities. At some point, it may no longer be beneficial. For example, how is the exploitation of wood. At one time, from my point of view, it was an extremely beneficial thing for the local economy, but now that we have shaved off all the mountains, it is no longer beneficial. We should reorient ourselves towards other economic solutions. I think it is possible with a little education and mental effort... solutions can be found to replace these traditions that at one time brought local benefits and now no longer do. Certainly, if we still deforest, we will not have any benefit from it. That would be an example. However, it is good to keep traditions and honour those that are still beneficial/from which we benefit and those that participate in our social, economic and cultural balance, but when they no longer participate in this balance and produce imbalances, no we still benefit from them, we can no longer call them traditions and healthy habits. They become destructive actions.” (RO1, P, R1)

In **TK1**, the Sarikeçililer community uses tacit knowledge from generations of living closely with nature, knowing precisely when and where to graze animals. This was expressed by one of our interviewees as follows: *“Even this child here can herd sheep. We rely on that, I mean. Everyone here can do every job; everyone is an expert at everything.”* (TK1, P, R4)

Another examples for an **intergenerational bi-directional learning** where younger and older participants co-contribute and learn is in **HU2** where children are involved in digital learning, and in **PT1** where volunteers of all ages learn from each other through direct involvement in agroforestry. In

that case younger participants bring new perspectives and technology use, while elder participants share traditional practical knowledge as cultivation techniques.

Across the 11 cases, we observe **an interplay** between **traditional place-based** ecological knowledge, evidence-based **scientific knowledge**, and community-related **process knowledge** that relates to an iterative learning. A blend of knowledge of all types is in the rural setting considered an important resource for resilience, but also for the preservation of cultural values. This is most accentuated in the Sarıkeçililer nomadic community in Turkey (**TK1**) where the access to natural resources (grazing areas) has immediate impacts on livelihoods and the survival of connected culture and traditions. Traditional knowledge is an integral component of the pastoralist and nomadic lifestyle, a blend of knowledge on seasonal cycles, water resources, animal behaviours and other knowledge that stems from the cultural practices. This differs from differently pronounced mixtures, blends of knowledge.

Exemplary expressed as *"Well, you know, some mountains, no matter how much they eat, it's of no benefit. It doesn't help the animals. I mean, a mountain can be sturdy; we call it sturdy. Sometimes you drink water, and when you drink water, you quickly get hungry. Some of them won't even let a person eat, but some water is solid. When you drink it, you immediately feel hungry. That's how it is in our place. Even how the wood that burns in the fire affects food or tea is known to us. If you bake bread with wood from pine trees, there will be soot. If you brew tea, it won't taste good, but if it's oak, it has a different taste. I mean, wood is better than coal."* (TK1, P, R1)

This interwoven knowledge is not exclusively valid for the nomadic group but also for many other participants in our cases: knowledge for pro-nature engagement is often based on **everyday experiences**, such as the observation of natural processes through farming, grazing or simply walking in close forests. For many interviewees, pro-nature knowledge is not merely a resource to be applied but a deeply embedded aspect of their **cultural identity and way of life**. Participants express that their knowledge of the land and its resources is **inseparable from their personal and collective well-being**, making environmental protection an act of preserving their heritage and ensuring the survival of future generations.

In RO1 and RO2 two different engagement cases, locals emphasize that their **connection to the land** goes beyond practical skills as they see nature as integral to their cultural traditions and ecological balance:

"In our family, the respect for nature and the benefits it offers us has been passed down from our ancestors. We respected the mountains and the forest for the water and clean air, the fruits, mushrooms and wood they provide us, as well as the soil where we grow our trees and vegetables. We also respected the domestic or wild animals that are part of nature and grow in nature. We were taught and later understood even better that man without nature cannot survive. And obviously we have a lot of traditions related to this aspect even since the time of our ancestors." (RO2, P R6)

The dynamic of connecting **knowledge from the past with the future** is highlighted also in cases where interventions are a considerable threat for the community. Such **temporal knowledge dynamic** is an enabler for change, for instance in **BG1** where knowledge about long practised farming practices plays a triggering role in the community action, namely the protest against the close by quarry.

We can continue this list with **HU1** where the need for transversal floodplain restoration is linked to place-based and historic events. The interviewee (HU1, P, R2) is quite self-assured about his knowledge about nature and the local environment. His anecdotes rather showcase how he could provide other people (even in official positions) with valuable information about (local) nature.

The same applies for **HU3** where the change of nationalisation in Socialism refer to an earlier past of a functional landscape with impacts in the more recent past:

“As far as I know this area was in the best shape before the nationalization process. Back then all farmers had an interest to keep their parcels tidy. Since then, agriculture has decreased, livestock and grazing have deteriorated, and invasive species have spread all around the terrain.” (HU3, P, R1)

When initiatives are **confronted with powerful entities** such as corporations or government bodies, they encounter knowledge challenges, especially in **BG1, BG2, RO1, TK1, TK2**. In some cases, such knowledge gaps can be bridged through **collaboration with external organisations**, such as enthusiastic third parties (lawyers, active networkers), scientific organisations, credible NGOs (like the WWF or more national active ones) and respected researchers.

In **BG1** we were informed how collaborations with ecological NGOs support the community access to legal and scientific knowledge – all needed to oppose developments that threaten their livelihood. In **RO2**, external support is crucial for locals who seek guidance in counteracting illegal logging practices that disrupt biodiversity.

In **TK2**, villagers have relied on legal knowledge and the support of a network of environmental activists to resist coal mining activities, demonstrating the importance of external alliances as urgent partnerships in strengthening local livelihoods and the surrounding nature.

In **PT1**, a steered **empirical learning through hands-on** agroforestry activities in workshops links with traditional agricultural knowledge to introduce sustainable land use practices.

The importance of blending formal scientific and legal knowledge occurs as well in other examples, **HU3** incorporates expert knowledge to support sustainable floodplain management, combining local skills with scientific insights provided by organisations such as WWF.

In **PT2**, participants rely on academic resources from universities, viewing them as reliable sources of information on ecological issues.

In **TK1**, a collaboration with a university highlighted how the community’s goat herding practices prevent wildfires, combining local and scientific knowledge to validate their ecological contributions. The inclusion of women in these educational processes is often critical, as they help bridge the gap between traditional practices and new scientific approaches.

In **PT1**, the presence of role models within the agroforestry project motivates participants, particularly women, to take on active roles for the progress of the project.

RO1 demonstrates the importance of activists in raising awareness on local level. They communicate to others the environmental impact of the active struggle in the area, encourage participation and shift the community mindset to become more aware of environmental issues.

The role of experiential learning, a practical **learning from doing and acquiring experience** can also be highlighted. This is an (group-) intrinsic way of shared knowledge and appears in the process and activities of the initiatives. In **PT1** (but also **HU1, HU2, RO2**), hands-on activities of planting and maintaining crops results in the participants’ connection to their newly improved livelihood, more commitment to sustainable use, conservation and protection of landscape.

HU2 includes experiential learning differently and offers learning opportunities through experiments by the youngest generation to introduce them to complex topics. A playground was designed to teach children water management approaches, which integrates fun with education to promote understanding for pro-nature care: *“If children are going to play through all the activities in the playground at the end of the educational trail then they will perfectly understand the basics of water*

management interventions, such as what meandering means, how a log dam works or how to use an Archimedean screw." (HU2, O, R2)

Throughout the cases, knowledge has two different primary notions. It serves firstly as a **means of resistance** and secondly as a **source of resilience**. Many initiatives depend on knowledge about the specific socio-technical systems. In order to act pro-nature, protecting their livelihood and natural resources knowledge is multi-faceted. Facets – and by far not all possible types of knowledge – include evidence-based information, e.g. the understanding of local or regional ecosystem determinants and processes. In some instances, insights respectively profound knowledge about legal processes; access to political actors; ability to **access to advocacy**. This list can be extended in many variations.

Gender plays in our cases a significant role in this dynamic, **women frequently emerge as key knowledge holders and advocates**, often bridging traditional and modern practices to mobilise and educate their communities. For instance, in **BG1**, a woman activist produces materials and visualisations that raise awareness and drive community action also **beyond the place of the initiative** (with national outreach). In this case the *essential role of women in knowledge management, practical dissemination and community mobilisation* is emphasised, obviously a demanding and time-consuming task requiring much creativity, persistence, professional management capabilities and empathy.

Common insights and overview of findings: Transformative change

Our fourth core question in RL2 explores the potential of the 11 cases to open **pathways toward transformative change**, which is understood as lasting shifts occurring on both personal and collective levels to change behaviour beyond the care for nature. The cases highlight **transformative signals to society**, emphasise hope and the potential for **creating a positive future through collective action**. Local communities showcase that meaningful actions could lead at some point to sustainable achievements, even under pressing socio-economic and environmental challenges.

In the 11 RL2 cases, transformative change **within and beyond** the initiatives emerge as an important outcome of participation in pro-nature and pro-environmental initiatives. This change extends **beyond the immediate activities** of the initiatives, manifesting in shifts in behaviour, newly established societal norms, and redefined collective values. However, transformation in the cases cannot be solely attributed to the initiatives themselves. It is shaped by a broader societal context, including education, resilience experiences, solidarity networks, and systemic conditions.

The change on **personal level** and in the social fabric are interrelated, for instance leadership in our cases appear along renewed (also gendered) role models, persons differently circumnavigate repressions related to their engagement, or live solidarity and social inclusion. Such role models inspire others to become interested, to participate in action – also beyond the pro-nature focus but often with significant importance for a resilient livelihood, e.g. addressing a current challenge with drinking water in one of our cases.

Transformative **change in a group** emerges as initial or increased political mobilisation, putting attention to the role of the present groups in the governance processes and administrative responses and calling for new solutions. In our cases environmental activists, participants and the grassroots organisers become policy advocates, but also disruptors towards more sustainable practice on a wider scale.

The project-related and carefully planned activities, as demonstrated in the three Hungarian cases (**HU1, HU2, HU3**), aim at achieving local change with broader effects on the water basin. These

activities blend diverse approaches to ensure a wider uptake, with a project-steered framework that **pre-determines signals** to society. For example, the systemic pilot approach in Hungary highlights the **replicability** of environmental action by addressing local water challenges while considering broader environmental impacts.

Differently, in **PT2**, volunteers perform habitat restoration, species monitoring, and environmental education tasks. These activities increase environmental awareness, encourage sustainable practices, and engage a broader community in pro-nature activities. Personal backgrounds and value systems influence the actions but also change during the involvement. The hands-on learning creates **emotional bonds to nature** and is also strengthening group solidarity.

Emotional engagement and local leadership in **HU1, HU2, HU3, and PT2** are key for adapting the social, cultural, and environmental contexts of each initiative. The structured and pre-planned activities provide **a replicable model** for similar actions on other locations.

Not all cases enjoy full **societal consensus regarding the value of their activities**. Conflicts with initially unwilling actors appear from the beginning or at a later point of action, such as in **RO1** where a temporal stop of the landfill appears as a significant achievement.

There is also no social consensus beyond the communities in **BG1, BG2, RO1, TK1, and TK2**. They give **replicability signals to smaller communities** with similar sustainability challenges. In **BG1**, the local struggle extends its limited outreach by **supporting similar local fights across the country**. One of the organisers expresses that their fight against the quarry sends an important signal to society. **BG2** exemplifies the power of solidarity by evolving from the fight against the incinerator to **address long-existing pressing issues such as drinking water supply**, creating an emblematic and solidaric movement for future struggles.

The situation in **RO1** diverges, as the local movement shifts partly from an environmental focus to governance matters, moving from the unfinished pro-nature struggle to a **renewal of a feasible community response**.

In **TK1, solidarity plays a crucial role in preserving pro-nature traditions within the community**. **TK2**, however, takes this solidarity further and becomes an emblematic movement for environmental action in the country, symbolising the **potential of unified efforts** and building upon what the previous civil struggle in Istanbul (Taksim Gezi Park in 2013) has started.

Signals from local communities in our “urgent” cases reach out beyond environmental topics, **evolving thematically on broader societal and governance (or democracy) issues**. Local initiatives stopping destructive projects do not only strengthen community cohesion but also extend solidarity to questions of governance, democracy, and administrative accountability. They demonstrate that environmental struggles can **spark transformative change on wider societal issues** (i.e. environmental justice, the role of administration, the functionality of administration and legal processes etc). Throughout our cases, activities were **enhancing community cohesion** and at the same **time putting a spotlight on a sustainable livelihood and local governance** issues.

Some **signals to society are visionary**, addressing the **collective power** of communities to **resist unsustainable development**. The fight for the Akbelen forest in **TK2** shows this in the most dramatic way. This movement demonstrates collective power, strength but also **signalises hope and visionary ideas for the community itself**. With socio-economic dependence on the forest and its associated traditions, this struggle blends and highlights the importance of **preserving both natural and cultural heritage**. The Akbelen case stands out as a symbol of how a community’s efforts can

transcend local concerns to deliver powerful messages to society about sustainability and solidarity.

Similarly, the **RO2** efforts emphasise on traditions and their importance for keeping nature intact while in that case community solidarity is **a challenge** and difficultly stretches out beyond the region.

In our second question on transformative change, we asked the interviewees about changes in their daily practice. Awareness of livelihood(s) and their development often extends to nearby natural resources that serve essential ecosystem services. These include with adequate care for the functionality components of protection from fire, dust, flooding, heat, as well as economic provisions such as grazing land for the community. Our cases as pro-nature initiatives and struggles focus on maintaining livelihoods, **emphasising the role of nature in sustaining everyday life**. This *reconnection* highlights the impact of intact surroundings on the own life, the need to develop sustained practice of everyday behaviours to move to sustainable practices.

Our interviewees acting pro-nature relate their engagement to the **daily use of resources** such as consumption (in many aspects), separately food, mobility, and partly to land use practice. Exemplary, and practically expressed in **HU3**, the pro-nature action directly impacts on the supply of firewood and heating for public buildings. The “reconnecting” to natural processes also inspires the re-evaluation of waste disposal and water management practices.

In some of our cases, the initiatives **directly address sustainable practices**. For example, the **PT1** community project focuses explicitly on *promoting sustainability*, similarly the educational components as presented in the Hungarian cases. Other pro-nature activities **link traditions to a re-newed environmental stewardship**, much emphasising on traditional sustainable land and resource use.

Even the **imaginary of past traditional lifestyles serves as a reference point for change**, where sustaining local livelihoods becomes a (past) benchmark for a sustainable everyday life. However, this connection is often challenged by modern lifestyles and emerging needs that exceed past imaginaries, exemplary present in the **TK1** where the traditional nomadic community tests out new solutions to enhance sustainability, like using solar power for electricity, while reflecting on their traditional roots.

While educational activities in **HU1**, **HU2**, and **PT1** often successfully address the younger generation, the emphasis on traditions connects to an **imagined past** that reflects sustained livelihoods, even though such practices may have largely disappeared or continue to be maintained out of subsistence needs as in **RO2**.

Options, alternative scenarios play a crucial role in triggering transformative changes. In **RO2**, participants reported no significant changes but emphasised *choosing environmentally friendly options when suitable alternatives are available*. Similarly, opting for local products or avoiding imported goods reflects sustainable practices, though these *changes are not always attributable* to the initiatives.

Awareness for more sustained consumption is a recurring theme. Activists in the **PT2** initiative prominently emphasise this aspect. Additionally, new information can shift attention to potential negative effects, such as resource overuse and contamination risks. As one **BG2** interviewee remarked in his motivation linked to change of practice as: *“I catch fish... I don’t want to go fishing tomorrow and find all the fish contaminated.”* (BG2, P, R1)

In **HU1**, the **need for better planning by administration** was discussed. A participant reflected on water retention measures and how they inspired him to use rainwater for washing or flushing toilets. He stated that he realised that only acting on individual level can trigger a true change: *“There is no*

effort or state-will realise such awareness-raising; therefore, people themselves have to start implementing them." (HU1, P, R2)

In **HU3**, a renewed awareness among residents has reduced administrative work. A local administrative actor explained as follows: *"My first offence had to deal with people stealing forest wood. This has completely changed by now. People realized that the heating value of the false indigo is much better than that of the stolen wood, so I do not need to bother with so many cases now in my office hours."* (HU3, O, R2)

Our third question on transformative change focused on the uptake of experiences from initiatives in similar settings. Our cases show that a sense of agency, new organisational skills are ingredients for continued involvement in similar cases in the future. First-hand experiences of collective action and (where truly appearing in our cases) tangible outcomes create sense for shared responsibility.

In **BG2**, the struggle against the incinerator project empowered individuals to believe in their ability to effect change and become active for wider relevant topics of the – that case a Roma community. As one participant expressed: *"Our fight shows that even small villages can stand up against powerful entities"* (BG2, O, R1).

This shows that the involvement in a single initiative **can inspire** persons to take on similar challenges in the future, in that case the pressing water supply challenge was mentioned during the interviews, which is a problem that affects more villages in the area. This interrelates also to the considerations shared about the signals to society that go beyond the actual pro-nature activity and transmit a positive hopeful message of empowerment.

In most cases, the pro-nature initiatives contribute to **developing self-confidence, leadership abilities and organisational skills**. In **RO2**, participants emphasised how their involvement-built capacities to address also complex social and political situations, noting also acting for the upcoming future generation: *"The initiative highlights the effort and love towards nature of some passionate people who want to leave a legacy to future generations"* (RO2, P, R4)

A contributor in the **PT2** case with its diverse activities and a focus on a wider geographical area expresses his readiness to contribute to other initiatives as follows: *"I would really like to be influential in this area, so that people feel inspired to take part in these kinds of activities because one of my goals is also to help causes and so on."* (PT2, P, R2)

The most negative personal impact was experienced in **TK2**, where the struggle to save the Akbelen forest was lost. One interviewee describes this as a turning point in their relationship with the state, marked by confrontations and violence. Witnessing the forest's destruction (with an intervention of the army) became a deeply traumatizing experience. While the interviewee was supporting the movement, it has also left the villager uncertain about the future. This emotion was widespread among villagers, many of whom began experiencing psychological difficulties following the Akbelen forest destruction in 2023. One villager captures the devastating impact, extending far beyond the physical, stating:

"I used to walk around the roof of the house until morning. I would wonder, 'Am I going to die tomorrow or during the day?' And when I slept at night, I would see the village in my dreams. For example, excavators had come, supposedly working, and I would wake up to that vision. Many times, I woke up feeling heavy like this." (TK2, P, R1)

However, despite the devastation in Akbelen, scenarios of positive futures are developed by the involved participants, cumulating hopes and many positive images, detached from the actually lost fights:

"Therefore, the cycle here needs to be broken, so that people can live in peace and prosperity, without economic or social difficulties, in an environment where they can greet each other with a smile while walking down the street. When someone falls, there should be a structure where another person can take their hand and lift them up. What this country needs is a society where love, respect, and solidarity prevail." (TK2, P, R2)

Interestingly, the **wider visions for a sustainable society** revolve around environmental justice, intergenerationally balanced use of resources and personal contributions to the challenges. They include the need for an educated society carefully using its resources, as expressed in **RO2**:

"First, they should stop illegal logging, we can still do something about it. [...] Many do not understand the connection between human actions and nature's revenge, even when faced with the negative consequences. For example, many do not understand why a landslide occurred in a forested area, some locals attribute it to the God's anger. So, a higher involvement in the education of local people and young people is needed." (RO2, P, R3)

Also, the future perspective expressed in **RO1** shows the need for a **wider change of the society**. A participant was expressing his concerns about the adaptation of the current value system as follows:

"Future development depends on the consciousness of those who live in various areas. In 15 years a lot can change, I'm optimistic and I think people will finally understand that it's important to protect the environment, not just our cultural values and it's important to adapt our cultural values to the environment because when they- established in the past, they made sense and were in balance then, but now many are not. So, we can always build new cultural values that also respect the environment and live in communion with it, because in the end it is in our interest." (RO2, P, R1)

Similarly, in **PT2** we hear a concern about the current economic system and its relation to nature:

"So, it's a question of values, which is the primacy of the economic, and therefore we have to bring the economic primacy to the environment." (PT2, P, R1)

Following the same pattern, addressing the need for a change of values - also in the urgent **BG1** struggle against the quarry development, there is a deeply rooted belief that the engagement is inherently driven by the **desire to secure a safe world for future generations** and protect the environment:

"What started as concern for my kids has become something much bigger. I've taken on more and more responsibility... it's a fight for the future of this place. It's not easy balancing everything, but it's worth it. My life now revolves around not just work and family but also fighting for our environment." (BG1, O, R3)

Also, the **change of administration** and obeying the rules is an important focus point which refers to rural inequalities and neglect of livelihood and traditions. A participant in BG1 expressed the wish for a positive future as follows:

"There is an unequal treatment of investors' interest and the traditional use of nature. Still, we speak about protected nature, we have to keep rules coming with the NATURA2000 status and at the same time the administration allows a quarry. This is not logical; this unequal approach has no future." (BG1, P, R5)

Finally, a more **responsible and guiding role of administrations and authorities** was pronounced as follows in PT2.

“This might sound a bit radical, but I think people who do something that harms the environment should be punished more severely because it's very lenient. If it's something that affects not just one person but the whole world, it doesn't make sense for the punishment to be so light.” (PT2, P, R7)

3.3.2. Change and gender+ inequalities within and across countries

In the 11 cases studies, we find inequalities and gender differences that highlight the roles of persons in the different process along context-bound and gendered hindrances and enablers.

As summarised in the Table below, we found manifold manifestations of gendered inequalities, such as missing access to tangible (car, public transport, equipment, land) and intangible assets (information), including such knowledge assets as role models. Information dissimilarities also included that women were not part of discussions of environmental topics, for instance due to a perceived lack of specialised know-how.

The gendered inequalities were sometimes made worse by other related vulnerabilities, e.g. age, minority status, education or low, subsistence-level income (unemployment) situation, which contributed for women having almost no voice in their communities. This reinforced the imbalance of decisive power structures that were often in the hands of privileged men community members. The struggle against such power dynamics was made more cumbersome by the traditional gendered responsibilities still prevalent in rural communities and often internalised as norms by affected women themselves.

Even if local administrations or external actors were sympathetic towards women struggles for a greater voice in pro-nature actions, they lacked the vision or resources to initiate and maintain proper forums for discussions where both genders could be equally represented. State policies could also act as hindrances towards elaborating more inclusive discussion options that included gender narratives.

Table 8. Initiatives’ outcomes, gendered aspects of change and highlighted inequalities.

Initiative- /case	Outcomes/results of Initiative (also beyond gender related)	Productive, “lived” gendered aspects occurring as change	Highlighted gendered/intersectional inequalities
BG1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opposing urgently the quarry development • Refiguring new sustainable futures • Linking livelihood with the surrounding nature • Solidarity and cross generational negotiation of new values 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Female leadership, as role models navigating complexity • Bridging types of knowledge including traditional knowledge hold by women • Meeting rural challenges of information and introducing a lively dialogue about a sustainable and inclusive future 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility, car access • Access to information • Lack of role models for managing complexity
BG2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opposing the planned incinerator • Involvement of often left out villagers by a wider initiative, some of them Roma • Solidarity of workers abroad with village • Redefining some feasible sustained futures and political engagement of community • Environmental awareness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in special ways as signature list • Including a female perspective in the discussion • Participation in defining a common future, partly traditional roles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility, no public transport • Exclusion from discussion of environmental topics (lack of specialized knowledge) • Importance of livelihood
HU1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the necessity of becoming active, awareness also on natures service for flood protection (nature-based solutions) • Involvement in practical care taking for floodplain areas on local level • Experiencing that one can change locally a wider challenge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project steered involvement to meet equality goals • Challenging traditional roles in the process • Change of thinking about own responsibility for actively meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Powerless, marginalised role of women from minority background • No voice in a little on gender entry points reflecting discussion

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement with the topic of pro-nature care in special forum • Employment opportunity for participants 	<p>challenges of the future on local level and linked to living realities</p>	
HU2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reinforcing previous experiences of change in earlier projects, experiencing how importance grows • Linking local change to organic farming and circular economy • Experiencing a pro-active community including the administration in the village to meet the flooding dangers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased importance of school children bringing the message home to families, also as digital ambassadors • Imaging process of possible futures contains gendered futures • Integrative and inclusive process potentially capturing wider opinions beyond technical knowledge, more embedded in local living 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural income limits for women along mobility concerns and marginalisation for ethnical reasons • No voice in the wider discussion for women, including farming as a topic in the hands of farmers who are men
HU3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserving and increasing the ecological status of the area of water catchment • Multi-purpose initiative (flood-risk mitigation; biodiversity protection; awareness-raising; dissemination, energy independence; better labour market situation) • Municipality and individual financial benefits from employment • Wood material for biomass use in homes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrating the lived participation in own life • Direct participation in manual work as wood splitting • Local community academy provides a forum for gendered perspectives addressing existing knowledge and new information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Imbalance of decisive power of land-use often in the hands of privileged men • Non-appearance of day-to-day and traditional knowledge from agender perspective
PT1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landscape regenerative pro-nature agricultural practice in a community led setting • Linking pro-nature action with the social fabric and a durable partnership of community cohesion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of land with guiding instruction • New rules and responsibilities, also confronting traditional roles of caregiving, cooking, distributing food 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to land and decisive power over is gendered • Traditional gendered responsibilities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation with strongly addressing vulnerabilities and immigrants • Re-connecting to nature for non-privileged households with many elderly and low average income people having now access to more fresh produce • Inspiring personal and community transformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reactivating knowledge from the past in the traditions of women, and trying out traditional cultivation in the neighbourhood on commonly/public owned land • Experiencing empowerment of migrant women, developing a sense of solidarity within a self-chosen group • Initiative as hub for a further exchange with other active groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recent funding cut needs new solutions for keeping social functions active that are highly relevant for women participants • Neighbourhood of multiple gendered and overlapping vulnerabilities including socio-economic status, age, migration and language barriers
PT2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hands-on practice of pro-nature maintaining an area • Peer exchange for like-minded volunteers, collective care pro-nature • Personally enriching participation as an experience with experiential hands-on learning opportunities • Experiencing public visibility of own contributions and message to society about the necessary transformative shift • Repercussion of complexity of the topic by a multifaceted volunteer programme 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusiveness and open approach respecting differences among participants in a rather open volunteer atmosphere including gender attentive practice • Room for experimenting with leadership of women participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Re-gaining power to change the environment in an inclusive and self-determined setting as contributing as volunteer • Entry points for environmental pro-nature engagement in a favourable inclusive group setting • Experiencing hands-on local change
RO1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regaining power about the livelihood and the already built garbage dump that should not be used in future • Specialised fight for intact nature after a massive technical intervention that could not be stopped • Context bound experiential learning from own interaction with nature is considered an important information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recurrence of the value of intergenerational learning, family values, this links to parent’s roles • Creating a liveable future and expressing it with a durable act of solidarity with the long struggle against the operation of the waste dump 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural context and persistence of gendered roles affect the pro-active involvement in the initiative and its punctual participation opportunities • Traditional roles in rural setting with limited income opportunities and resilient agriculture practice

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience of resisting to mainstream land use even the garbage dump that was funded by EU funds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A call for change of societies values and expression of solidarity also by vulnerable e.g. in signature lists. Collective mentalities linked to nature are discussed, but gendered approaches remain neglected vis a vis traditional gender roles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linking the source of existence with wider development beyond traditional use or knowledge • Gendered participation and inclusiveness remain undiscussed, and no gendered voice appears with the specialised legal fight
RO2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reforesting of over-exploited areas within reach of livelihood • Identification with nature is generally an asset for re-enforcing pro-nature activities and occurs with the activities or with the observation of (also frustrating) change • Defending the nature for the future generations • Educating people about illegal practice leads to a change of mindset 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a better shared vision about a liveable future with a look on the next generation impacts the gendered roles as well in education • Images about feasible collective action and solidarity open visionary perspectives also for the observing, rather passive contributors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elderly women with limited mobility are concerned by the development • Subsistence economies with traditional gendered work distribution and roles • Unbalanced and gendered educational chances and responding achievements in the past • Unheard voices with limited fora to inform about gender specific matters at all, low social self-esteem in view of contributing to discussions that are not accessible • Detrimental environmental practice lacks a forum for discussion that might be influenced by female expression of non-appreciation (like waste burning of trash)
TK1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserving the long-standing pro-nature sustainable living of nomadic pastoralist practice with biodiversity positive outcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of a strong women leadership provides important role model also for keeping nomadic lifestyle and its traditional setting alive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional division of labour and existing norms about masculinities and femininities • Gendered access to education due to seasonal moving and schooling challenge

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Struggle for the state acknowledgement of the pro-nature value of the grazing service carried out by the nomadic practice • Dispute over settlement and grazing rights • Solidarity association appeared as an alternative way of defending the nomadic rights after the struggle in 2004 • Strong female leadership formed new role model for engagement of all included persons • Opening a future perspective relate to the practice of pastoralism and its legal access to grazing land, water and forests • Continuing interaction with many like-minded supporting organisations and scientists over time also to gather scientific insights (e.g. on productivity and eco system services from pastoralism) • Presenting a liveable image of eco-friendly living with pastoralism practice to inform about existing alternatives of own practice (not meant as an invitation to join) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leadership and guidance extend to many lived community events including the appearance to public with involving many faces of the community • De-facto inclusion of women participants in the association despite no ID • Self-pride and confidence of the pastoralist is strongly linked to the representation of women in public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility appears gendered, it occurs and influences e.g. the official participation in the pastoral association as no photo is available etc.
<p>TK2</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appears as highly visible fight against state corrupted land exploitation vis a vis local livelihoods, known in rural and urban areas • Struggle against the livelihood and forest destruction by state backed coal mining, using in a traditional way the forest is carried out since long time and is continued 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-organised by vulnerable groups and taking an active gendered voice in the fight through female leadership • Spreading of a pro-diversity inclusive norms and values among the community • Stepping in the traditional governance system as elected village head 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small scale farming and traditional gender roles cumulate e.g. gendered hindrances as mobility • Impact of state policies repeating current discriminative gender narratives and reproducing corresponding gender roles in society

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activation of many supporters for the causa on national level due to increasing frustration with public administrations practice • Establishing a structure of self-organisation and integrating activism in personal lives has been a functioning, but remains a challenge after the lost fight in 2023-2024 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open minded dialogic view on non-traditional approaches also from the LGBTQI+ movements 	
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Discussion and conclusions

4. Discussion and conclusions

The analysis of the pro-nature and environmental initiatives across the 11 cases reveals multi-faceted insights and a specific understanding of how **motivation, participation, knowledge, and wider results of transformation** interconnects. With the cases we capture inseparable components of environmental stewardship, relate to wider community building and the development of resilience. We have highlighted the intersectional, overlapping enabling conditions and barriers for contribution across all the covered cases. Across the four dimensions, we come to the following conclusions.

Motivational aspects as interlinkage of personal, community and system triggers

Immediate environmental threats drive persons to take on matters, leaving little choice but to become active. The sense of responsibility for future generations and perceived ineffectiveness of authorities pushes individuals to take action in solidarity with nature and its instances, with communities, and its livelihood.

Participants are often responding with pro-nature activities to direct and urgent threats to the existing livelihoods. This is present in **BG1**, where the struggle against the quarry is -exemplary- tied to protecting the UNESCO heritage and securing future generations' livelihoods. Many more examples have similar reference points as **BG2** with a concern on air quality; **HU1** with linking to drought and floods; **HU2** with a multidimensional response to flood or drought with new practice; **HU3** with livelihood aspects of flood management and local economy; **PT1** with multiple pro-nature actions for a neighbourhood; **PT2** rooting to the national park and voluntary action. Emotional connections to the environment, such as childhood images, memories in **RO1** and **RO2** or deeply rooted cultural practices, traditions in **TK1** and **TK2** all the listed reference points play an important to be highlighted role for the mobilising of committed communities.

In several cases, **systemic failures** and also allegations of corruption emerge as motivating factors. For example, **BG2** participants resist the incinerator plans due to its harmful environmental implications and its association with opaque regional (environmental) governance practices. Similarly, in **HU1**, participants emphasise the inadequacies of top-down water management policies, highlighting a positive project-based shift towards widely accepted community-driven, small-scale solutions.

Social dynamics and aspects of inclusive engagement

Participation and the related collective **power of solidarity** plays a crucial role for the active movements. Group dynamics (often seen in the hands of women) and social cohesion around pro-nature environmental topics support participatory processes. Continuity, developed maturity, and acceptance of support from external sources makes sustained action and participation of persons or groups possible which are otherwise often not involved. Convincing role models who navigate participation barriers – such as repression, social exclusion, and in most cases limited resources – are essential for commitment and solidarity across more diverse groups.

Participation within the initiatives is demonstrated along a wider scale of engagement, ranging from grassroots activism to strongly structured organisational processes or extending to wider alliances beyond local action. Gender and social dynamics play significant roles in shaping participation. Women emerge as key leaders in several cases, exemplary in **BG1** and **TK2**. Here, active roles in decision-making and advocacy influence and redefine gender norms, many other cases challenge traditions in the process. At the same time, participation is determined or limited by systemic barriers

and hindrances. These are limitations in mobility, economic constraints including fear of job loss, and earlier but continuous social exclusion, as visible in **BG2** and **PT1**, where migrants and economically disadvantaged individuals face challenges in fully engaging.

Cross-generational participation appears repeatedly across our 11 cases. For example, the pro-nature initiative in **PT2** emphasises the role of youth in fostering behavioural change within families and communities, similarly this appears in **HU1**. Differently and with a backwards pathway of looking, **RO1** and **RO2** participants emphasise the value of traditional knowledge as passed over through generations. The specific intergenerational practices in some cases might limit a true and comprehensive cross-generational engagement. Despite such challenges, many initiatives successfully thrive with strong personality, re-emphasising cultural practices and reaching out to wider alliances. Exemplary is a practice seen in **TK1**, where nomadic communities who live distant from each other yet succeed to unite in a struggle for their rights and protect their communal way of life.

Knowledge interrelates to traditional, scientific grounded and experiential learning modes

Explanations of the role of knowledge relate to different sources and types of knowledge that enable the active care for nature. Formal or informal organisers and participants undergo knowledge exchange processes in a bi-directional way. Knowledge is not strictly fact-based or rational, but includes intangible heritage of practice, a tacit understanding passed through generations. Intergenerational knowledge transfer, personal experiences.

Exchange of such different types of knowledge remains important when a community group is confronted with powerful actors such as corporations or administrative structures. Knowledge gaps emerge and well-informed organising persons or sub-groups help to navigate these challenges, related to organisational, political, and legal knowledge – especially when sustained action is a necessity.

Knowledge plays a core role in the process of empowering individual citizens and groups to take pro-nature or pro-environment action. Within the cases, we observed and received explanations how dynamically a blend of traditional, scientific, and experiential knowledge determines the activities of the separate communities. In **TK1**, nomadic communities leverage their ecological and geographical knowledge to advocate for sustainable practices. In this case the group challenges misconceptions about their impact on fire, on the environment. A discourse starts that provokes the negotiation about current mainstream views in the society. Similarly, **HU2** combines traditional farming techniques with state-of-the-art water management methods to achieve ecological restoration and food security, in other cases it impacts on firewood provision as in **HU3**.

The importance of a variety of knowledge-sharing mechanisms for pro-nature initiatives becomes evident from initiatives like **PT1**. Workshops, peer-to-peer learning, and intergenerational exchanges enrich the participants understanding of sustainability practices, opening up new avenues for a wider audience. Differences in access to knowledge, especially among marginalised groups, remain a true challenge (as well as in **BG2**). Exemplary in **RO2** participants of the initiative express the need for a more accessible, relevant education and awareness programs to “counter” misinformation and to enable a much wider participation and understanding. In all the covered cases experiential learning relates to empathy, role models, potential peers, and a willingness to also deviate from institutionalised facts that emerge from governance challenges.

Transformation ranging from individual awareness to a wider systemic change

In the 11 cases, transformative change appears to express itself directly with persons who have become increasingly aware of their daily habits beyond the actual care for nature activity, such as waste reduction and water saving. This extends beyond activism or small-scale conservation efforts.

Women leaders in our cases appear as role models who circumnavigate repression, promote solidarity by living social inclusion, and inspire others to take action.

Behavioural change as group emerges as well with increased political mobilisation and around governance matters. Often started locally, we see in the covered initiatives some that inspire national movements, act as role models e.g. they share their experiences or risk a legal process at court to safeguard other territories from similar threats.

The transformative impacts of the initiatives are observed at individual, community as livelihood, and wider systemic levels. At the individual level, participants report increased environmental awareness and shifts in daily behaviours, such as waste management and sustainable consumption, as seen in **PT2** and **TK2**. More explanations with results on living practice can be found. Community or livelihood level transformation include especially the strengthening of social cohesion and the development of local pro-environment and pro-nature solutions to global challenges, as exemplary evidenced in **HU3** and **BG2**.

At the systemic level, several initiatives contribute to policy advocacy and a wider structural change extending beyond the livelihood of the specific community. In **TK2**, the Akbelen forest movement successfully elevates local struggles to the national stage, challenging destructive mining policies and fostering broader solidarity. Still, the struggle does not end positively while the emblematic achievement is the formed and strong solidarity network. Similarly, **BG1** participants request better accountability of the administration in its governance. They also relate this to a “futureable”, equitable resource distribution. This shows the potential of grassroots initiatives to request and influence long needed systemic reforms (see also our findings on corruption above). Still, durable systemic transformations depend on addressing existing inequalities; securing institutional/administrative support; and, from a time- and urgency perspective, on mid- and long-term engagement.

4.1. Paths and links to transformation

RL2 has developed key insights in four key areas that relate to the paths and links to transformation with the analysis as presented above. Here we highlight for each of the four distinct questions the main processes identified for a transformative path.

Motivations and triggers for pro-nature engagement

Motivations and triggers for becoming active for pro-nature initiatives relate to an interplay of personal, community (as a place of livelihood or group), and the initial environmental challenge as the cumulating main focus. Across the 11 RL2 initiatives, our findings conclude that citizens are less driven by an “abstract” desire to protect nature. Instead of activities for the protection of wild habitats or specific species, a protected area, **participants are driven more by material, tangible concerns** linked to the living conditions or livelihood concerns. For many participants, *safeguarding the quality of life* (and livelihood) is a primary motivator. The **intrinsic connection of livelihood, “in between environment and daily life”**, particularly in rural areas, appears as a main motivating factor.

Participation and behavioural transformation

Participation in pro-nature initiatives appears as a start in a **transformative experience**, for individuals and subsequently also their communities. The collective nature of participation in a group of active citizens links to solidarity, community bonds, and can relate to behavioural change. Participants frequently describe their involvement as a kind of response to limitations of individual acting. In many cases, women play a central role in pro-nature initiatives by taking leadership responsibilities that give them chances to incorporate unique perspectives in the struggles or pro nature actions.

Knowledge types as enablers of change

Knowledge has an important role as enabler of pro-nature activities, it is a precondition for enabling individual citizens and communities to take action. Across the eleven RL2 cases, different kinds of knowledge appear. The different types of knowledge appear as important resources, enablers for first starting and maintaining pro-nature activities over time.

A special role relates to place-based knowledge and traditional knowledge, which is rooted in local culture. Experiential learning, gained through hands-on activities, can be an occasion to become familiar, to gain insights in ecological processes. Also, scientific and legal knowledge complements place-based, traditional and experiential insights, such knowledge is important for the urgent struggles with the administration.

Knowledge-sharing *within* communities enables behavioural change, the sharing creates opportunities for intergenerational learning and as appearing in all our cases: for collective identity-building and a shared mindset or objectives.

Pathways for a wider transformation: advocates and hopes

The insights from the 11 RL2 initiatives, its communities, give some indication how pro-nature initiatives influence societal transformation. Local actions in our cases relate to specific systemic inequalities, but they are also inspiring communities to look out for alternative pathways for a more sustainable living. The appearance of a wider solidarity outside of the community, outside of the immediate livelihood is experienced in all of our cases. This makes inequalities also more visible, the engagement processes and the true participation gives new visions and hope, inspires for new engagements in other causes.

Participation in the pro-nature activities leads to more ownership, looking out as well for – also visionary – systemic long-term solutions for the livelihood, for the community rather than focusing on short term socio-economic goals or gains.

4.2. Policy crossovers

Core thematic synergies for our topics of **caretaking for nature and environmental stewardship** relate to the following topics in other research lines:

RL1 Valorising local knowledge in the frame of the community-based disasters' management and mitigating exposure

Our cases are closely linked to intense environmental consequences such as flooding, dust hazards, water scarcity, poisoning risks, which are part of a broader biodiversity crisis. One case involves the irreversible destruction of a forest for coal extraction, while others are still actively fighting similar exploitation threats. The shared experiences within these movements have as well built a strong foundation for group resilience, as communities see a future need to prepare in front of potential catastrophic events. The participative experience also prepares for future crises, although we hope such situations never materialize to test this resilience.

RL5 Food security and livelihoods, RL6 food values

Several cases relate thematically to this challenge. Traditional living, resilient agricultural practice but also food safety that is endangered by economically threatening development projects with expected devastating impact on the environment can be highlighted. Traditional food, also for economic survival relates to some of our cases and interrelates to intergenerational learning, intangible heritage or tacit, often not shared knowledge. A gendered knowledge difference exists and relates as well to traditional role models and practice, often 'challenged by intergenerational views.

RL7 and RL8 Mobility

We see that gendered mobility was expressed in some of our cases. This might be a valid starting point for discussions on environmentally friendly mobility options in rural contexts. Mobility in cities, especially in more privileged settings, often contrasts much with mobility patterns in rural areas. We experienced that elderly individuals and others lack access to public transportation (also most extreme, having erected new stops but no operating bus). While this was not a primary focus in our 11 cases, side notes on mobility highlight the challenges of limited or gendered mobility limits of villagers. Discussions on environmentally friendly transportation often focus on urban settings but might leave out rural realities.

Figure 6. Synergies across research lines in ACCTING related to RL2.

4.3. Research limitations, gaps and directions for future research

The current research gaps are listed here as an inspiration for a further coordinated discussion across the ACCTING research lines.

(a) Intergenerational and emotional dimensions of behavioural change

The cases in RL2 point to the importance of **role models and actions that embody cultural capital as a further to be understood “driving force of change.”** Cultural capital, with reference to Pierre Bourdieu’s conceptualisation, connects to symbols, ideas, tastes, and preferences that relate to strategic significance within society. A critical research question would be to investigate **how role models influence the shift in practices and how cultural capital evolves** during these processes of change.

Role models might operate on different scales. On the one hand, we see roles in **leadership positions in pro-nature initiatives, they are visible agents of transformation (as in BG1, TK1 and TK2)**. On the other hand, smaller-scale role models embedded within traditional settings like in RO1, HU2 may not have a similar broad outreach but can drive significant change in household-level environmental practices, they refer to smaller scales. While we have received indications of external actions influencing these smaller-scale practices, this area remains experimental underexplored. Respondents in our interviews emphasised the importance of traditions, but the nuanced relationship between **traditions** and the integration into changed environmental practice requests in our view further attention. A better understanding how traditions relate to environmental challenges might open up thinking on **new pathways for significant behavioural change**.

Cultural narratives, emotional motivations (as captured in RL2) and intergenerational dynamics of knowledge are present in our cases, exemplary in RO1 and RO2. We see in our rural examples where cultural narratives and collective memory (as reference to a past) influence pro-nature behaviour and environmental engagement. **Gendered perceptions of responsibility and**

action in family structures, especially where caregiving roles extend to environment might be an important research focus with reference to emotional aspects and traditional cultural practice.

The role of children as agents of change, as transmitters of change and knowledge in families, the resulting value change would be an interesting topic that might open up new insights how pro-nature behavioural change relates to the intergenerational dynamic (as reference to a future and the future generation). As an inspiration, we consider also the relevance of digital tools for environmental mobilisation and knowledge leverage a possible starting point e.g. to look on the role of social media for participation in pro-nature activities.

(b) Gendered dimensions of leadership, resources and urgency

In the RL2 cases we see active women that overcome the barriers with powerful engagement and action. The cases showcase **significant contributions of women** as leaders, still they are not always powerful participants in pro-nature initiatives. Women's roles, especially in urgent grassroots movements such as in **BG1**, **TK2** and **PT2** meet many structural and cultural barriers. We refer to traditional norms, practically to caregiving responsibilities especially in a rural setting, or mobility challenges. Those factors determine and limit leadership within the local actions in our focus.

There is a strong belief - embedded in the observed initiatives - that it is hard to influence systemic decision-making processes that impact on the own livelihood. This belief impacts on the wider results and the leadership positions within environmental movements. It is unclear, how gendered the perception of female leadership influences the communication with institutions, the administration and the process of outreach to other initiatives. An interesting research direction can be the exploration of **gendered leadership approaches**, the influence of a present **livelihood perspective** and empathy with local citizens respectively as components of the success and sustainability of environmental initiatives.

The transition to leadership roles and related pathways might also feed a scientific discussion on gendered perspectives and power relations in the process (complementary to the first research question in RL2). Some of the cases relate to strong leadership subsequently often succeeding to **overcome systemic barriers**. We think that an important component of research on gendered participation and leadership roles would be to explore and explain how **timely urgency interrelates e.g. with gendered networks** in the rural area, especially such networks that help to overcome structural barriers. More dimensions for gender studies can be derived from other findings in RL2, here we have listed only a few perspectives that can be wider elaborated.

(c) Solidarity across pro-nature initiatives with wider transformative environmental actions

With this research area we emphasise on the gap of knowledge related to the **transformative power of solidarity** between local environmental (or pro-nature) initiatives and **broader socio-political movements**, such as women's rights movement, the LGBTQI+ activist movement, exemplary in this (incomplete) list veganism and animal rights. Such research has the potential to **explore and explain the connections and the integration of environmental, ecological concerns with wider social challenges** and help to understand **how reciprocal (bidirectional) solidarity influences activism**. A focus can be exemplary set with a focus on livelihoods and how they link to concerns beyond local environmental struggles. A significant research direction would be to uncover how interconnected movements associate with collective transformation and new, innovative approaches to meet multiple goals of sustainability, inclusivity, and reflect environmental and social justice. Further, the **role of alliances for giving vulnerable, marginalised citizens a voice or the bidirectional empowerment of the included groups** can provide new insights reflecting the collective action, also to understand who has been left behind. Limits - and challenges for research- appear from the overlapping of

objectives within alliances; cultural or governance influence related to local challenges or wider changes; aspects stretching from knowledge exchange processes to mutual learning dynamics; the process of revoking of positions within alliances where diametrical opinions form a specific discourse.

(d) Capturing the perspective of those who observe or stay indifferent and passive

We think that environmental egocentrism and the role of livelihoods as present in our cases are drivers of pro-nature behaviour – at the same time we have not explored what can provoke potentially exclusionary. Our cases in RL2 excludes partially those **who signalise indifference or act as passive observers**. We observed scepticisms about the validity, the efficacy of **small-scale actions vis a vis tremendous global challenges** all in stress situations of limited resilience, little resources to contribute along specific barriers. The perceived irrelevance of environmental issues to daily challenges of survival, combines with hierarchies, perceived lack of power or influencing cultural norms and the resulting intersection provokes a rather indifferent, passive position. Still, the **neglect of the challenge** is an important topic for behavioural change and relates to inclusivity. Explaining the non-inclusion further would add substantially to the understanding of pro-environment behavioural change or give insights in the specific refusal dynamic – especially in emblematic pro-nature and livelihood related actions or initiatives. A critical research question might focus on the **drivers of “indifference”, passive observation or the complete neglect of the challenge**. Perspectives about **the possible leverage of such positions** might become guiding principles for more inclusive action. A multidimensional approach can provide insights beyond the current RL2 work that focused on mostly successful active contributors rather than those staying passive, disengaged and neglecting the problem(s). **Social exclusion, social dynamics as peer pressure, and self-efficacy (and many more motivational aspects) can be explored to understand passivity better**. As well socio-demographic differences, special vulnerabilities and the role of environmental literacy can be separate focus points of examining passivity. RL2 has been starting to explain the motivations and triggers for becoming active. We think that the identification of fictional triggers, potential tipping points for becoming active **in future** would be a fruitful approach that might lead to better insights in the participation challenge and current positions of neglect.

(f) Values and behavioural change in the context of culturally embedded traditions

Our cases in RL2 inform and explain change and societal transformation in mostly rural **settings and often references to traditions were made by our interviewees**. As a deeply embedded moral, ethical, and cultural system, **values** were intentionally not a primary focus due to methodological challenges associated with the limited research period. Still, perspectives of sustainability and intergenerational justice with reference to traditions and **associated values** were shared within the interviews. We consider exploring values related to pro-nature, pro-environment, and generally sustainable practices in such contexts as an enriching and complementary research direction that we want to highlight in the RL2 inspired future research agenda.

An important research area would be a focus on aspects of **collective mindset**, such as (collective) **moral** responsibility, as well how **learned and inherited environmental practices** influence values and subsequently contribute to pro-environmental caretaking. This value system might (among others) refer **to traditions, habits** learned from parents, the wider family as grandparents, or a mindset related to “imaginary” ancestors. Traditional environmental practices can be either detrimental - such as field burning of trash or dumping waste into water bodies, but also pro-nature beneficial as demonstrated in the RL2 cases, all expressing different values and value system processes. We see a link of traditions and intergenerational and environmental justice as well. Understanding how traditional practices relate to values and behaviours could offer insights into **pathways towards more sustainable behaviours** in rural and vulnerable contexts.

(g) Further interesting topics:

The following research directions **were elaborated in an ideation stage**, some of them relate to multiple research lines within ACCTING:

- Developing a stronger **multispecies dimension** of caretaking stretching beyond the current definitions of ecological research. A direction to follow this approach can be to explore how non-human entities, such as animals, plants, and ecosystems, function as agents of transformation within pro-nature care-taking initiatives. Such dimension might relate to a specific dynamic, it might impact on ecological practice(s) and societal narratives. Further considerations if current research in the field of ecology does not already integrate the multi-species aspect sufficiently are necessary to understand the solidity of the concept of multi-species dimensions vis a vis a (declared to be) natural sciences inspired and rational world. Different schools and scholarly traditions have evolved in the humanities and the biology sciences or human geography, and it is worthwhile to re-assess the overlapping meanings and use the chance to bridge different approaches across disciplines. Re-imagining a wider perspective beyond the anthropocentric viewpoint also bridges to a further research direction. The re-invented **role of commons** in pro-nature and ecological initiatives might open new avenues for research. This relates to land use, the role of administrations and the public, the (future perspective) of legal roles as agents taken on by representative groups constituting/representing the commons also in current processes. As a revival of old traditions and a renewed concept, the impact of a wider understanding of commons for local pro-nature caretaking initiatives can be further explored with research. The applicability of the concept of commons for pro-nature action has been proven but the **role for behavioural change and especially vulnerable groups** would be an interesting and multidisciplinary research topic. The concept of commons as well relates to a specific change of political space. The extension of the political space from currently prominent political topics as employment, healthcare, education and many other prominent political discourses to other urgent topics like

environment can unfold a specific dynamic. Engagement in pro-nature action redefines in our cases political engagement, extending the concept of commons further, opens new perspectives. Change of **political space with introducing commons in the discussion** can be a productive research topic opening new perspectives for the society. It can visionary open up new perspectives beyond nowadays decision-making venues (as the above listed political spheres, topics) to “living” natural spaces such as forests, meadows, rivers and microbiomes.

- Based on the different cases in RL2 we came across **perceptual differences of ecological disasters** in the past as they were referenced by our interviewees. Studying further **how local citizens perceive ecological disasters in their neighbourhood** might give action guidance based on the experiences how to **relate local action to the sensitivity developed from a past disaster**. Notably RL1 addresses this topic further.
- A closer research perspective of **funding policies and their impact on pro-nature action** can open new insights (as followed in other research lines in ACCTING). A thorough look on the results of different EU funding instruments, the different funding instruments as evolving on national and regional level and the impact on behavioural change might be productive. Such research can focus exemplary on the **past changes in EU and national funding policies** e.g. for land use and continuing the RL2 efforts also on **how policies have influenced local pro-nature caretaking initiatives**. This might refer to policy results as adjustments of land management practice, (most linked to RL2) community-based environmental engagement and generally (pro-)nature governance. We consider a research approach important, that relates to the role of **participatory governance**. An important question can be to reflect on funder’s **expectations and how funding goals interrelate with often urgent local community goals**. Our reference case in RO1 gives insights in divergence of funding goals and local livelihoods. In parallel, we experienced in RL2 several initiatives that operate with the support from external funding as in **HU1, HU2, HU3** and add this research question here. We are well aware that the determination of results and impact is rather considered an evaluation task, but in our view, this can evolve in several research questions with practical impact of ownership of policies etc.

4.4. Directions for policy recommendations

The presented directions and ideas for policy recommendations relate to an urgent need for gender-sensitive, inclusive frameworks that address structural inequalities. They relate to institutions, initiatives, specific barriers evolving for vulnerable groups, knowledge specific processes. In the recommendations we add specific references from the cases that showcase potential effects of change of policy. Finally, we see a rather **interwoven framework of policy strategies and the actual policy delivery and implementation**, referring to the pro-nature behaviour of individual persons and groups, and we see in both instances a need for change. The interplay with environmental initiatives might open new avenues of change for the most vulnerable citizens with limited voice.

By integrating institutional reforms, promoting inclusive knowledge sharing, and supporting grassroots activism, policymakers can create enabling environments that amplify diverse voices (such as present in our cases), foster sustainable practices, and bridge the gap between grassroots efforts in initiatives and a true systemic change. This approach ensures that at least project based environmental initiatives are equitable, impactful, and potentially scalable.

Policy Recommendations for Gender-Inclusive Environmental Initiatives

The analysis of RL2 highlights the need for gender-sensitive and inclusive policy interventions to address structural inequalities, also to empower marginalised groups of the society. Systemic barriers should be overcome to enable balanced, equitable outcomes of policy interventions.

(a) Gender sensitive governance

Across all our RL2 cases, women's contributions often remain invisible or stay at more informal grassroots levels. We recommend that institutional mechanisms should sufficiently (1) amplify women's leadership and (2) ensure equal participation in decision-making processes. Formally this can be reached with gender quotas in local governance bodies and environmental bodies, committees to institutionalise gender equality in representation. Examples of RL2, like **TK2**, where a woman acts as head of the village, showcase the transformative potential of such practices.

Beyond this (3) gender mainstreaming should be embedded in environmental policies to address specific constraints faced by women, such as limited mobility as experienced in (**BG1, TK1**) and gender bound access to resources (**HU3, BG2**). As a solution exemplary capacity-building action for local authorities could be a tool to adopt gender-responsive and inclusivity for a fair decision-making.

(b) Mobility challenges in rural settings relate to gendered participation

Mobility disproportionately impacts rural women in their livelihood and limits the participation in local change processes. Mobility concerns the access to information, peer networks, and generally to participation opportunities. This impacts on the participation in local decision processes, it limits women's agency in processes. As one solution we think that remote decision-making processes might open up new chances, but digital barriers appear subsequently, a barrier that only a younger generation might circumnavigate with having the relevant technical knowledge. Traditional caregiving roles as well impact on rural mobility, on the participation in important local decisions. Financial incentives and support, such as grants or childcare services, can enable participation of women with caregiving responsibilities, in RL2 we find such scheme in **PT1**, where support for low-income participants is part of the pro-nature activity.

(c) Inclusive knowledge sharing

Technical expertise remains in processes a male-dominated matter, women’s specific, in some instance traditional knowledge is often undervalued or remains unshared. Establishing new frameworks for mutual exchange of knowledge like community knowledge hubs might facilitate a more equal exchange opportunity. We see exemplary in **HU3** efforts that integrate traditional and scientific knowledge in a process of mutual learning, in the dedicated community academy. We consider accessible and gender specific training programs and knowledge exchange opportunities important, they have a potential to empower rural marginalised groups as elderly women or minority groups. Such inclusive knowledge sharing practice can ensure that a multitude of valuable contributions can be recognised and considered as an important resource for sustainable community solutions.

Intergenerational learning processes, which highlight women as knowledge holders are as well important. RL2 cases like **RO1** and **TK2** inform how women’s participation impacts positively on efforts to preserve cultural heritage and the environment.

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